

An Analysis of How Serverless Architecture Benefits the Development of a Scalable Web3 Wallet Aggregation App

By

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Abstract

This dissertation explores the integration of serverless computing and blockchain technology in developing a Web3 wallet aggregation application, WalletScan. Positioned at the intersection of serverless cloud technology and digital economies, WalletScan embodies the potential and challenges of employing serverless architectures to manage blockchain data effectively. Through a practical application framework, this study investigates the scalability, cost-efficiency, and developer experience of serverless systems in supporting complex, data-oriented blockchain applications.

The research delves into the deployment of WalletScan as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) platform, enabling users to scan blockchain wallets and analyse cryptocurrency transactions. The application leverages Firebase for authentication and serverless backend operations, Vercel for serverless frontend deployment, and integrates sophisticated features like Web3 onboarding and WalletConnect to ensure secure user interactions.

Significant findings indicate that serverless architectures facilitate rapid deployment and scalability while minimizing operational overhead and costs. However, challenges such as third-party API integration complexities and the inherent limitations of serverless platforms in handling granular control over backend processes are also documented. This study provides a balanced perspective on the feasibility of serverless technologies in the emerging field of Web3, underscoring both their transformative potential and the need for enhanced tools and strategies to address their limitations.

By examining WalletScan's implementation and operational dynamics, this dissertation contributes to the understanding of how serverless computing can be optimally harnessed in blockchain applications, offering insights that are vital for developers and industry practitioners navigating the evolving landscape of digital finance and decentralised applications.

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1. Introduction

Recent innovations in cloud technology have completely changed the way we create, use, deploy and manage web applications. Among these technologies, serverless computing stands out as a *major* change, introducing a way to get web applications deployed to the internet without the traditional need for managing servers at a granular infrastructure level, where the “[*developers*] are only concerned with the desired functionality of their application and the rest is delegated to the service provider [such as Google, Vercel and others]”, (Shafiei, et al., 2021) allowing for a fast “*time-to-market*” (cygnismedia, n.d.).

As digital economies grow, blockchain technology has become increasingly important, creating an “*emergence of other derived technologies, such as decentralized finance (DeFi) and [dApps, which] has fundamentally transformed people’s daily lives and profoundly impacted digital businesses.*” (Banaeian, et al., 2023), marking the beginning of a new kind of “internet” per se, commonly referred to as “Web3” that is decentralised, open, and is “*rewiring how the web works, using blockchain*” (Stackpole, 2022).

Although serverless architectures have a lot of potential, there is still not enough clear understanding about how effective they are in supporting blockchain-based, data-oriented applications, especially when it comes to scalability, cost-effectiveness, and the workflow of development from a dev (testing) environment, to staging and lastly to production. This gap of knowledge makes it hard for developers to fully embark and justify using serverless technology to embark in creating blockchain-oriented websites.

This dissertation looks at how serverless computing and blockchain technology can work together in creating a scalable aggregation-based Web3-oriented web application. By examining how these two technologies combine, **this dissertation aims to find out the potential advantages, pitfalls and overall experience for developers using serverless architectures to build strong, scalable web applications for aggregating data on blockchain-based wallets and activity**, with a bold focus on trying to create and simulate a real-world Web3 start-up, with the website appropriately nicknamed and referred to throughout as “**WalletScan**”.

1.1. Defining App Build & Context

“WalletScan” is meant to be a tool, classified under a Software-as-a-Service website product, in which allows users (who have intentions and desires to make money, as well as being an active part of the crypto space) to “Scan” wallets on the blockchain to receive heuristic and pre-aggregated data and analysis of said wallets’ activity, which, in turn, provide the users with indicators of what cryptocurrency “tokens” (also known as smart contracts) to buy or sell, what wallets to look at, and more, increasing the chances of making money through crypto.

For those unaware of what “tokens” are, a good example is to compare it to stocks. A stock, like AAPL, MSFT on the Stock market, have a market value, where 1 share of stock could be worth a certain amount of US Dollars. It can rise and lower in value. The same concept applies to tokens, except anyone can purchase a certain portion of the supply of tokens in a decentralised manner, using web3 wallets (stored, usually, on the internet browser of the user locally) to interact with a decentralised exchange. *“A decentralized exchange (or DEX) is a peer-to-peer marketplace where transactions occur directly between crypto traders. DEXs fulfill one of crypto’s core possibilities: fostering financial transactions that aren’t officiated by banks, brokers, or any other intermediary. Many popular DEXs, like Uniswap and Sushiwap, run on the Ethereum blockchain”* (Coinbase, n.d.). A “wallet”, can contain these tokens, as well as the transactions associated with purchasing or selling said tokens. The transactions as well as what tokens are inside the wallet are publicly readable (not publicly writable or changeable) for others to see, which allows for WalletScan to access this information and “Scan” wallets containing it.

As crypto enthusiasts like to trade tokens (like trading stocks), analysis is usually done on wallets and their trading activity of tokens manually by looking at portfolios online or looking at block explorers, such as Etherscan. *“The skill to read blockchain transactions and data are essential for anyone to go from a beginner to a pro blockchain user. It can help you gain crucial insights into cryptocurrencies. ... blockchains store all transaction data in a transparent public ledger. However, while all data is readily available, you may find it challenging to access and understand accurate information without the right tools. ... To help you with that, there exist block explorers.”* (Musharraf , 2023).

Although block explorers are useful in providing fast, raw transactional data as displayed in Figure 1, they are not aggregated and displayed in a heuristic view to allow the user to easily make decisions on what tokens to purchase and/or what wallets to look at.

Figure 1 - Etherscan Block Explorer Displaying Raw Wallet Transactional Data from etherscan.io

The screenshot displays the Etherscan interface for a specific wallet address: 0x8314f2766944fEB78e16d5311a94D23DA6E4ID5. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Overview:** Shows the ETH balance as 0.106974272164319542 ETH, with a value of \$330.25 (at \$3.087.18/ETH). It also shows token holdings totaling \$27.87 (47 Tokens).
- More Info:** Includes private name tags, the last transaction sent (0xafefc4217d3... from 8 days ago), and the first transaction sent (0x7e955f93c4c... from 485 days ago).
- Multichain Info:** Displays a multichain portfolio value of \$1,266 and 5 addresses found via Blockscan.
- Transactions:** A table showing the latest 25 transactions out of a total of 747. The table includes columns for Transaction Hash, Method, Block, Age, From, To, Value, and Ten Fee.

Transaction Hash	Method	Block	Age	From	To	Value	Ten Fee
0xafefc4217d3...	Execute	19630732	8 days ago	jetijonny.eth	Uniswap: Universal ...	0 ETH	0.00431191
0x7acc27ab08...	Approve	19630731	8 days ago	jetijonny.eth	0x4d948C9d...5076eC453	0 ETH	0.00091138
0x7def9d88624...	Execute	19578116	15 days ago	jetijonny.eth	Uniswap: Universal ...	0.25 ETH	0.00596466
0x7616d874d2...	Transfer	19578113	15 days ago	Binance 18	jetijonny.eth	0.3062906 ETH	0.00074298
0x4ac04958ba...	Execute	19553424	19 days ago	jetijonny.eth	Uniswap: Universal ...	0.08 ETH	0.0039705
0x3799dd43a7...	Deposit Trans...	19528456	22 days ago	jetijonny.eth	Base: Base Portal	0.3 ETH	0.00220864
0xd0d104e189f...	Deposit Trans...	19520751	23 days ago	jetijonny.eth	Base: Base Portal	1 ETH	0.00189124

This is where “WalletScan” comes in, providing an opportunity to fill an actual gap in the industry. The creation of this start-up website and its inherent features to “Scan Wallets” with a streamlined, user-friendly interface, with an end-result of displaying aggregated data, allows for many computing concepts, especially in web development, to be utilised, allowing for a well-rounded simulation of what a developer using serverless technology in combination with web3 concepts would undertake to develop such a tool, giving a stronger chance to answer the dissertation question.

2. Aims & Objectives

This chapter outlines the key goals and objectives of the research, detailing what the dissertation aims to achieve and guiding the investigative efforts. These objectives clarify the research direction and inform the methodology. By articulating these goals, the chapter focuses efforts on achieving the set objectives, enhancing the research's effectiveness.

2.1. Primary Aim

The primary aim is to develop a secure, scalable blockchain data aggregation web application, simulating a startup to assess the benefits and challenges of using serverless architecture for Web3 websites.

2.2. Objectives

1. Conduct research on existing, similar academic & industry materials related to serverless architectures and blockchain data aggregation.
2. Identify the crucial and necessary features for the web app as well as determine the types of data aggregations and crypto indicators beneficial to users, prioritising user needs and potential blockchain integration challenges.
3. Create and research the architecture and relevant technologies required for serverless computing, ensuring the compatibility with the planned web3 features of the web app.
4. Investigate and choose suitable technologies, tech stack and frameworks.
5. Find, research, and integrate relevant third-party APIs for data gathering and aggregation, ensuring the application remains an efficient and respectful consumer of the provided resources.
6. Investigate good methods & strategies to ensure the application scales efficiently, preparing for industry standards as well as the possibility of mobile app integration, while also developing a plan to lower potential costs as much as possible with increased user activity.

7. Outline and plan the initial database structure, ensuring compatibility with the intended serverless architecture and desired scalability.
8. Develop wireframes (if possible, based on scope of timeframe) and detailed designs for the application's user interface, and explore open-source libraries or software to enhance the front-end functionalities and decrease the development time.
9. Launch a live, closed-beta, proof-of-concept of WalletScan at <https://walletscan.io> or <https://app.walletscan.io>, simulating a real-world application with essential features like "Scan" and wallet management fully operational.
10. Create a custom survey designed for developers (in this particular case, the researcher) based on post-evaluation of key features related to web3, serverless architecture, web apps in general and bespoke features of WalletScan, allowing for evaluation and analysis of the primary aim.

3. Literature Review

The literature review examines existing research on serverless architecture and blockchain technologies, identifying gaps and highlighting this dissertation's unique contributions. It explores serverless technology's role in scalable Web3 wallet applications, laying the *foundation* for the methodology and implementation analysis.

3.1. Serverless Technology & Architecture

In an extensive, recent blog by *Arkhipov*, it displays and compares the best types of serverless frameworks “*by their price, advantages, and disadvantages*” (Arkhipov, 2022) which allows for a better understanding of what framework was to be used for the dissertation. In the blog, the top two choices were “*AWS Lambda*” and “*Google Cloud Functions + Firebase*” in that order. Although it states AWS Lambda as the top choice, it mentions specifically for Firebase that it allows natively for “*setting up triggers that will activate responses to user actions and changes of application*” and that “*Google Cloud Functions is cheaper than Azure and AWS*”. This is of extreme importance for two reasons. Firstly, the fact that “*triggers*” are a key, easy-to-use feature apart of Firebase provides more confidence when developing the specific ‘Wallet Scan’ feature, allowing for easy “*tracking*” changes of said ‘Scans’.

As per (Kesavan, et al., 2023) “*[Firestore] scales to millions of queries per second and petabytes of stored data; notable current and past users include the New York Times and BeReal, as well as a prominent social media app and a mobile game each with over a hundred million users. Importantly, at low scale QPS (queries per second) and storage consumption, Firestore costs close to nothing.*”. Firestore is “*a NoSQL serverless database with real-time notification capability, and together with the Firebase ecosystem greatly simplifies common app development challenges by letting application developers focus primarily on their business logic and user experience.*”. This clearly not only displays the great scalability of this specific serverless platform, but also highlights that it allows developers to focus more on the business logic rather than infrastructure management – which is crucial in designing a relatively large system such as WalletScan for the purpose of the dissertation (based on the imposed time constraints).

Another example of some crucial literature is (Uunonen, 2023) “*Backend as a service in web development*”. This source touches upon building a demo application and going through the structure of a “Backend as a service” architecture, which Firebase can be ultimately classed as. Within the source, it touches upon a lot of different serverless vendors and their features, but specifically, as an example, “Hosting” is talked about with Firebase. Hosting the app is an essential component of web development, and it appears as if “*Hosting is done with the automated deployments from GitHub repository, or with the CLI. With the firebase deploy command, CLI let[s] the developer choose what services are deployed. It automatically detects what services have been updated from the current deployment.*”. Considering Firebase looks like a strong contender on the database side as well as the authentication side of implementation based on how streamlined deploying is from *Figure 2*, it’s highly unlikely that most developers would use *just one* singular proprietary platform for everything as there are many different options to consider for each part of an application. Therefore it’s important to look at other services as most teams and developers would like to create the best product in the least amount of time.

Figure 2 - Deployment process in Firebase CLI. (Uunonen, 2023)

```
$ firebase deploy

=== Deploying to 'food-thesis-app'...

i deploying storage, firestore, hosting
i firebase.storage: checking storage.rules for compilation errors...
+ firebase.storage: rules file storage.rules compiled successfully
i firestore: reading indexes from firestore.indexes.json...
i cloud.firestore: checking firestore.rules for compilation errors...
+ cloud.firestore: rules file firestore.rules compiled successfully
i storage: uploading rules storage.rules...
+ firestore: deployed indexes in firestore.indexes.json successfully
i firestore: uploading rules firestore.rules...
i hosting[food-thesis-app]: beginning deploy...
i hosting[food-thesis-app]: found 4 files in dist
+ hosting[food-thesis-app]: file upload complete
+ storage: released rules storage.rules to firebase.storage
+ firestore: released rules firestore.rules to cloud.firestore
i hosting[food-thesis-app]: finalizing version...
+ hosting[food-thesis-app]: version finalized
i hosting[food-thesis-app]: releasing new version...
+ hosting[food-thesis-app]: release complete

+ Deploy complete!
```

One example to challenge the previous advantages to Firebase Hosting is Vercel, a very powerful serverless platform giving developers a great experience of getting their website

deployed, especially with SSR frameworks like Next.js. (Gage, 2023) provides a detailed overview of how they simplify the deployment process for web applications, especially going through its strengths over platforms like Firebase Hosting. *"Vercel lets teams deploy their frontend stupidly easily, separately from their backend."* This ease of use is critical for projects using server-side rendering SSR frameworks such as Next.js, where Vercel's integration offers significant advantages.

The blog also notes, *"Vercel, and products like it, are specifically built for deploying frontends and making all of the above work as easy as possible."* This focus on frontend deployment contrasts with Firebase Hosting, which, while robust for hosting static and dynamic content, do not provide the same level of support for SSR frameworks that require more granular deployment strategies for use in WalletScan. The direct integration of Next.js with Vercel, where *"every function in the 'api' folder automatically gets deployed as a serverless function in Vercel,"* showcases Vercel's superior handling of SSR, highlighting why it's a better choice for developers prioritising this technology. It's truly incredible how far the world has come in terms of getting a website deployed to the web, all for free (until you scale up, of course).

Furthermore, Vercel's smart approach to deployment is designed to be highly efficient and developer-friendly, as illustrated by the feature of deploy previews: *"When you open a new pull request... Vercel automatically tries to deploy that code on a new server so you can see how it looks before agreeing to apply those changes."* This functionality is part of what sets Vercel apart, offering a streamlined workflow not just for deploying applications but also for testing and integrating new changes seamlessly, much like a developer would need to do in a real-world environment, supporting the dissertation's aim of simulating a different environments much like a real-world web application. This justification here also allows for a fair comparison against the standard monolithic, traditional approach for web applications, where it would take a tremendous amount of time, research, dedication and setup to create this kind of deployment flow CI/CD in a non-serverless based application. For example, you would have to setup and manage different branches, GitHub repositories, environment variables, SSH, all yourself, utilising platforms such as Github Actions, CircleCI, etc.

3.2. Blockchain, Aggregation & Comparable Systems

Existing academic resources lack specific guidance on developing websites for tracking and aggregating blockchain wallet transactions using serverless architecture. This dissertation addresses this gap by enhancing understanding of blockchain operations, wallet functions, and cryptographic details crucial for website interactions.

One perfect example of some good academic material is by (Suratkar, et al., n.d.) which gives a detailed, granular look at the different types of cryptocurrency wallets and how they're used, such as the mentioned "*Web Wallets*" and "*Hot*" or "*Cold Storage*" wallets. This is beneficial material since the implementation of the WalletScan integrates the use of web3 wallets to allow the user to link their own wallet to the website. The reason they do this with WalletScan is demonstrate the SaaS side of the website, in which users receive the ability to "Scan Wallets" if they pay a certain amount of money to do so.. However, since WalletScan is a crypto-based website, it employs the idea that users must purchase a certain amount of a 'utility token' to get access to different tiers on the website (which is demonstrated through working proof of concept with a test token known as 'USDT'). "*Utility Tokens are usually backed by a project, an application, or a dApp with a definable benefit (like access) and intend to provide access digitally to an application or service by means of a blockchain-based infrastructure.*" (Angelo & Salzer, 2020). Think of it like this – instead of paying a monthly subscription to access the services of WalletScan, users would, instead, simply purchase and hold a certain amount of the token supply (theoretically, through a DEX) to gain access to different tiers and features of the site, which, based on the token price, allows for developers to pay for server costs by using their own 'team' supply. Creating a token and launching to a DEX is out of scope for the project, but \$USDT is used as a placeholder regarding feature authorisation and permissions.

In regard to the "Scanning" and data aggregation side of things from the blockchain, A source by (Schär, n.d.) gives some relevant insight on the more abstract architecture of how Decentralised Finance, coined as "*DeFi*" in the crypto space, is defined. Within the source, it provides a relevant diagram (*Figure 3*) of the "*DeFi Stack*", which allows for clarification on where WalletScan is defined and what layers it utilises. Based on the explanation of the different layers, it appears that the website built for the dissertation is primarily attached to

the “Application” and “Aggregation” layer for the user-interaction part, but the data primarily comes from the “Settlement” and “Asset” layers.

Figure 3 - DeFi Stack - (Schär et al. 2021)

3.3. Comparable Systems

Existing aggregation sites offer detailed data analysis for individual wallets on various blockchain networks, covering token holdings, transactions, and sometimes interactions with decentralised exchanges (DEXs). However, these sites often fail to explain the significance of the data or allow users to customize their data scans.

WalletScan introduces "Cross-Wallet Analysis," a unique feature that aggregates data across multiple wallets, unlike the typical portfolio views of other systems. This feature not only enhances user understanding by providing more comprehensive data insights but also explores the use of serverless technology to reveal potential benefits and challenges associated with blockchain activities. This approach aims to simulate a real-world application and demonstrate the unique selling point (USP) of WalletScan.

Nansen

<https://portfolio.nansen.ai/> (Nansen is a basic example related to this dissertation's goals, managing multiple wallets and offering data visualization through graphs and charts. However, it lacks clear indicators for interpreting data and does not support aggregated analysis across wallets—a key aspect of this dissertation. Additionally, Nansen does not specify whether it uses serverless or serverful technologies.

Figure 4 - Nansen Dashboard for a portfolio of wallets

Zapper

<https://zapper.xyz> (Zapper) is visually stunning, minimalistic in design and intuitive to use, while also demonstrating basic functionality of wallet / token aggregation (Figure 5)

Although it is not as varied as Nansen, the look and feel is exactly what would be expected in the dissertation's implementation. Design is a very important factor with the use of research of comparable systems, allowing for inspiration.

Figure 5 - Zapper Dashboard for a singular wallet

The screenshot displays the Zapper dashboard for a wallet named `jetlijonny.eth`. The interface is dark-themed and includes a navigation menu on the left with options like Home, My Profile, Lists, NFTs, DeFi, and DAOs. The main content area shows the wallet's profile, a net worth of **\$728.29**, and a breakdown of 78.12% in the wallet and 21.88% in NFTs. Below this, there's a section for filtering balances and a table titled "Wallet" showing the following data:

Token	Price	Balance	Value
ETH	\$1,685.50	0.1515	\$255.40
BNB	\$215.93	0.8491	\$183.35
ETH	\$1,685.78	0.0658	\$111.00
ETH	\$1,685.50	0.0088	\$14.87
WBTC	\$27,214.00	0.0001	\$3.35
SOV	\$0.00000000399	238M	\$0.95

4. Methodology

This very important section of the dissertation is crucial! It details the approaches and processes used to tackle the research problem. It describes how both qualitative and quantitative data were collected as well as analysed, using a mixed-methods approach. The section also outlines the **tools and technologies used, such as development environments and cloud platforms**, linking these back to insights from the literature review. By explaining the procedures for system development and data collection through an advanced, organised, and well-rounded survey meant for a developer (in this case, the researcher), the methodology ensures that the dissertation is well-placed to stand a chance in filling the gap in research, in a way. This setup not only helps structure the investigation but *also* prepares for evaluating the outcomes against the set aims and objectives, ensuring the dissertation is clear.

4.1. Research Problem Classification

The main research problem is to gain more understanding of an under-researched topic. More specifically on discovering *how* serverless architecture *benefits* the development process when creating a scalable web3-based website involving complicated data aggregation techniques (leaning towards finding out a gap in knowledge on the more developer-based practical side of implementation).

4.2. Types of Data

As mentioned previously, both qualitative and quantitative data were collected as well as analysed, using a mixed-methods approach. It's important to note here that both were used and evaluation simultaneously, with a stronger focus on the qualitative data.

The data collected is of a Primary Source. Although the technologies and architecture were built, in a way, with Secondary Sources of Information and Open Source tools, the resulting conclusion to the dissertation will solely be based on Primary Source data coming in proxy from the custom implementation and a dedicated survey.

4.3. Data Collection Type 1 - Implementation

Due to the nature of the dissertation, being more focused on the actual implementation of web development computing principles through a practical, simulated, real-working, proof of concept application – the evidence and practical useability of the application (being a website) plays a huge part in the *validity* of the dissertation regarding coming to a suitable conclusion because, for example, if no application was built first-hand, the developer experience and retrieval of weaknesses and benefits would not occur or be displayed without using less-reliable secondary sources. Demonstration of a working implementation is key.

It's essential to understand that without Implementation or a working product, it would be fundamentally more difficult to answer the research question at hand as well as create more types of data to collect towards answering the question.

(The full methodological approach for the Implementation is available on section 4.6)

4.4. Data Collection Type 2 – Developer Survey

After Implementation and the working proof-of-concept has demonstrated actual use and web3-based functionality (through proxy of developing with serverless technology), an advanced and bespoke survey was created for the developer (in this instance, the researcher). This singular survey consisted of a multitude of questions containing qualitative and quantitative questions for each key section of Implementation, highlighting, in detail, the developer-assumed benefits, difficulty, weaknesses, problems, overall experience and oversights of the application built, with questions focused in on the area of serverless technology, aggregation, industry-standard website development features and practices, and many more – to gain a full understanding of what a developer encountered in the web3 serverless scenario, providing insight on filling the gap of knowledge.

4.5. Classification of the Conclusion

The data that was collected allows for language to be analysed for the qualitative-based questions, which, in turn, allows for a conclusion to be reached on the research topic through

the creation of assumed benefits, weaknesses, and opinionated stance on exactly how serverless technology has benefited or disadvantaged creating a web3 data-heavy application. The final conclusion leading to providing an answer to the research question will highlight areas of weakness, overall benefits, whether an application like this is maintainable, profitable, what the potential long-term problems are, how the developer felt throughout working with the technologies and problem-solving throughout, what could be made better from a serverless standpoint, and, overall, whether serverless architecture is *worth* using over potential serverful (traditional) architecture for a data-aggregation web3 website on this scale.

4.6. Approach & Development Technology

Below is listed the detailed approach that not only created the web application, but allowed for a better chance of coming to a more reliable and verifiable conclusion to answering the research question. These steps made it possible to create a comprehensive analysis and challenging, yet meaningful developer experience, and were created with pre-existing developer-based knowledge and crucial research from the Literature Review section in mind.

The initial step involved researching common features of blockchain wallet-based web applications that offer data aggregation, aiming to establish a "Wallet Aggregation App" as per the research standards. This exploration was crucial for understanding existing interfaces and identifying a "Unique Selling Point" (USP), essential for differentiating the app in a competitive market. A USP is vital for revenue generation, crucial for maintaining server operations under a pay-as-you-go serverless model. This approach supports scalability—essential for handling up to a hundred thousand users—and highlights the importance of unique, appealing features that not only attract users but also ensure financial viability through methods like subscriptions.

The next step was to design suitable wireframes and concepts for the user interface design. For this part, (apart of Pre-Implementation or '*Analysis and Specification leading to the Proposed Design*'), based on the comparable systems within the Literature Review, it was clear a great digital tool was needed that was also used in industry for most design work. The tool used was Figma to create these concepts and diagrams.

Next, an overall abstract theory was needed to gain an understanding of *how* the features were going to be implemented, such as “Scanning Wallets” in a streamlined way for the users. This involved creating necessary draft diagrams demonstrating potential user flow, and the backend of the system (what happens after a user presses a button on the site to do something functional, for example). This was an important step as it displayed whether or not serverless architecture had potential limits or future problems when implementation came along. The tools used to create diagrams were Figma and Eraser.io.

The next part was to begin developing the proposed system based on the researched theory of architecture and by using a various amount of tools and technologies relevant to the stack. Based on the relevant literature researched, it was clear that the following technologies were to be used:

Serverless Technologies Used

1. **Google Firebase (Firebase Auth, Firebase Functions, Firestore, Realtime Database)**
2. **Google Cloud Functions (for more control over scans than Firebase)**
3. **Google Cloud Tasks (For handling third-party rate limits)**
4. **Google Cloud Secret Manager (Handling environment variables)**
5. **Vercel (Pro Plan)**
6. **Vercel KV Storage**
7. **Vercel Hosting**
8. **Framer Motion (For Landing Page)**

Third-Party APIs Used

1. **Transpose.io (Wallet Aggregation with scalable custom SQL Queries)**
2. **Alchemy.com (Theoretical Wallet Balance Updates with Webhooks)**
3. **WalletConnect.com (Connecting web3 wallet to WalletScan via Browser)**
4. **QuickNode.com Token API (Getting current balance of utility token)**

Web Frameworks + Stack Technologies Used

1. **Next.js (Backend + Frontend Framework)**
2. **React (Backend, Next.js is built on this)**
3. **TypeScript (Instead of JavaScript, used for type safety)**
4. **NPM (Package Installer)**
5. **Node.js**
6. **GoDaddy Domains (for <https://wallethscan.io> DNS)**
7. **SQL (PostgreSQL, for use with Transpose.io)**
8. **Firestore Document Database (as mentioned)**
9. **Realtime Database (Firebase, for updates on scans and monitoring triggers)**
10. **GitHub (Repository Management)**

UI Libraries

1. **NextUI**
2. **NextUI Pro**

**A full list of packages will be provided in the source code.

5. Pre-Implementation - Analysis & Specification

This chapter displays and provides a full set of the essential requirements of the system, and displays an abstract, pre-implementation set of specifications that inspired and lead to a concluded implementation. For clarification, the diagrams and specification presented was made before implementation was started properly - and is only an abstract version of the resulting build. For final specification, see Section 6 of the Implementation.

5.1. Theoretical (Initial) Problems & Solutions

***Below are a list of theoretical classified problems faced during the BEGINNING of pre-implementation, which had to be thoroughly thought out to understand how the entire application could look. These are conceptual. Not final. For final designs and the result of the work, see Section 6 (Implementation).*

Problem 1: What could the Serverless Architecture look and function like?

Initially, it was understood that, considering the use of Vercel and Google Cloud, the service architecture would look like below as shown in *Figure 6*.

Solution 1:

The User would make a request through their browser (client-side) to the Vercel backend in some way – either through Server Actions and/or Route Handlers. It was assumed that, due to the ‘SaaS’ element of the website, requests would have to be processed through middleware with Next.js and Vercel. After certain ‘IF’ conditions (permissions, security, etc), the request would be processed and passed to some kind of Cloud Function, whether that’s on Vercel or Google Cloud or Firebase.

It's also worth noting that there had to be some kind of authentication involved. Considering Firebase has ‘Firebase Admin’ – which allows certain actions to occur server-side only, a session token could be used to access the user details for authentication and authorization.

Figure 6 – A General Serverless Architecture Backend User Interaction

The code that runs on the backend would obviously tie to ensuring features are run, such as “Wallet Scanning” and performing analysis.

Problem 2: What frontend technologies should be used to ensure the following?:

- Fast Performance
- Cheap Costs to run web frontend
- Fast Development Time
- Allows developers to easily integrate in to working on the project like a real world business
- Great documentation
- Superb modularity allowing for open-source packages
- Great potential to abide by current industry standards (a vague overlook)
- Great SEO customisability to get outreach

Solution 2:

Front-End Technologies:

- Next.js, React
- Typescript (and some Javascript)
- TailwindCSS
- Framer Motion (Serverless Hosting App for Landing Page, AND the package)
- NPM
- NextUI

- NextUI Pro
- Other open-source packages

The selection of Next.js with TypeScript, TailwindCSS, NextUI, and NextUI Pro as the technology stack plays a pivotal role in addressing various project challenges while ensuring efficiency, performance, and accessibility. Next.js stands out for its ability to lower costs and enhance app performance through features like the app directory, server components, client components, caching, and server-side rendering. Its superior SEO capabilities, compared to React alone, mark a significant turning point in the development process. Recognising the importance of visibility in search engines for any successful website, the decision to make use of Next.js was driven by its comprehensive SEO support, offering a substantial advantage over other frameworks. It's widely supported too.

TypeScript is chosen for its discipline, promoting cleaner code and reducing the likelihood of errors, rather than for personal preference. It facilitates easier integration for new developers joining the project, ensuring that the codebase remains accessible and maintainable. The preference for TypeScript is also supported by its widespread adoption in developer guides, further simplifying the development process compared to JavaScript.

NextUI (Free, which NextUI Pro is built on) and NextUI Pro are integral for enhancing the website's aesthetic appeal and accessibility, leveraging react-aria for building accessible components. These libraries not only accelerate development time but also ensure the site's usability and visual attractiveness. The investment in a lifetime access solo plan licence for NextUI Pro, valued at \$199, is justified by the significant time savings offered by advanced pre-built components that can be, and have been, customised. However, it is very important here to note that the project's code can be understood and utilised without the necessity for others to purchase a licence, ensuring open access to the development work. The initial challenge of mastering TailwindCSS, upon which NextUI is built, was overcome through dedicated learning and application.

Problem 3: What backend technologies should be used to ensure the following?:

- Fast Performance
- Cheap Costs to run
- Fast Development Time

- Allows developers to easily integrate in to working on the project like a real world business
- **Scalable** to thousands of users
- Great documentation
- Great potential to abide by current industry standards (a vague overlook)

Solution 3:

Back-End Technologies:

Firebase (Largely Serverless Based)

- Firestore
- Authentication
- Firebase Admin

Vercel (Largely Serverless Based) WITH NEXT.JS

- Hosting & Deployment
- Vercel KV Storage
- Vercel Serverless Functions
- Vercel Edge Functions & Middleware
- Vercel Caching

Google Cloud (Serverless Based)

- Cloud Tasks
- Cloud Functions

In the development of the web3 wallet aggregation site for the dissertation, a strategic selection of backend technologies could be used to ensure amazing scalability, efficiency, and a seamless user experience. The core of this infrastructure utilises Firebase, Vercel, and Google Cloud, each offering unique advantages tailored to the project's requirements and overall question the dissertation is trying to answer regarding serverless technologies.

Firebase serves as the foundation, with Firestore chosen for its scalability to handle thousands of users, robust querying capabilities, and ease of use. The NoSQL system is vital for storing aggregated scan data of wallets and tokens, offering free usage up to a certain limit.

Firebase Authentication is also used, enhancing user experience by supporting various sign-in and signup methods, including Email, Google, and Microsoft, and more.

Firebase Admin is integrated to manage backend processes effectively, allowing actions to be executed serverlessly with Next.js. The reason this could be (and was) used is to reap the benefits of Next.js's server-side-rendering advantages if need be.

Vercel complements this setup by providing hosting and deployment solutions that leverage a CI/CD github workflow for seamless updates and environment management. The platform's support for Next.js ensures that code is optimally converted into functions, middleware, and caching mechanisms. This ensures speed and fast development time.

Vercel KV Storage offers temporary, high-performance storage solutions, while serverless functions, middleware for user flow management, and caching are utilised to optimise performance and reduce operational costs. The KV storage specifically is used for mainly temporary data, whereas Firestore is for more persistent storage. The reason KV Storage will be used is due to the fact that when running background tasks on scans, this allows for temporary tracking and organisation of these tasks. It's important to note that the main tasks to process wallet data and token data will be stateless and asynchronous, so if multiple tasks are running under one main scan (subscans), there needs to be a way to keep track of all of them together without race conditions occurring across multiple tasks, essentially providing state to the stateless tasks.

Google Cloud's role is pivotal, with Cloud Tasks and Cloud Functions enabling scalable, stateless, and asynchronous operations essential for managing third-party API rate limits and performing wallet scans. Cloud Tasks provide a distributed queue system to prevent API

overloads, while Cloud Functions facilitate the execution of scans and other actions, ensuring the platform can efficiently serve a growing user base.

This combination of serverless technologies forms an amazing backbone for the web3 application, is definitely one to be proud of after connecting everything together, addressing the intricate challenges of blockchain data aggregation and analysis with serverless technology. By leveraging the strengths of Firebase, Vercel, and Google Cloud, the project aims to offer a scalable, efficient solution for tracking and interpreting the activities of significant cryptocurrency wallets, converting to data for use within a useful, heuristic view, thereby empowering users with actionable insights for informed trading decisions.

Problem 4: As the main practical use of the application, what will the process look like in regard to scanning wallets, aggregating data, storing that data, and accessing that data in a secure way, abiding by third-party rate limits?

One of the biggest challenges is, of course, figuring out how to scan and aggregate data (for multiple wallets) and get that data back to the user in the fastest way possible - but - ensuring that the application scales properly to ensure users are not put at a disadvantage due to sloppy and inconsiderate backend processing.

Solution 4:

One part of the solution is to make use of Transpose.io, specifically their Custom SQL Endpoints, to create custom ways of aggregating certain data points. Before diving deep in to that, it's important to understand the context of what exactly is being aggregated. To start with an example, let's say that a user on the website WalletScan, wants to see the following data about their chosen, tracked wallets:

"A user of WalletScan, who is scanning 200 wallets, may want to see a Pie Chart view (as well as a List View) of the tokens that appear most in the wallets.", AKA, Shared Held Tokens.

For example:

- SHIBA token appears 25 times (is in 25 wallets) across all the wallets. - PEPE token appears 23 times (is in 23 wallets) across all the wallets.

This is just one tiny example of a great data point that gives potential indicators to the user about what tokens to purchase / invest in.

Now, as each data point, like the above, can be completely different to another one, this is exactly why Tranpose.io's custom SQL Endpoints may be (and was) used, since it's incredibly versatile. However, the complexity of the SQL query and flow of processing data will be different PER data point. This is the challenge.

This leads to a crucial next point. How are these queries initiated, and how would a user start a scan, wait for it, then read it? - This is where a lot of the key backend components come in to play, and one of the biggest problems solved. Let's go through the theoretical and initially thought-of flow:

1. A signed-in user, with a valid amount of the websites' utility token to make the scan in the first place, makes a scan with many data points being collected. This data is sent to a NextJS Serverless Function to be checked.
2. The serverless function will calculate the amount of subscans to initiate and start based on the data provided by the user, per data point.
3. The serverless function will push one or multiple tasks to the Queue (made with Google Tasks) so that the API calls to transpose are called at a certain rate within each serverless Google Cloud Function (such as 1 request per second).
4. The Cloud Functions make the transpose requests, and, once a response is retrieved, either store the temporary data in Vercel KV Storage or store in Firestore. It would only store in Vercel if the task is a Subscan (a subscan is part of one main scan. It's used when a scan needs to be split up in to multiple, so that it can reduce processing time and reduce the amount of Transpose credits used). It gets stored in Firestore if it's the final subscan of the main scan by querying Vercel KV checking the state, and

if its the last scan, combine all of the aggregated scan data together, then, check if all that data is over the 1MB document limit on Firestore. If it is, shard the data in to multiple documents, if not, store in one document.

While the user is waiting, the Cloud Functions will update the Vercel KV store, to which the user will long-poll to view the loading status. Using Vercel KV instead of Firestore here to potentially reduce read costs.

An initial diagram demonstrating this flow is made below in *Figure 7*.

Figure 7 - Initial Scan Flow

5.2. Initial Design UI Concepts + Wireframes

In the below Figures, are the designs and initial concepts (made with code, and made with figma) before implementation was complete. This was to gather an understanding of how an

application would work best to suit active cryptocurrency users based on the Comparable Systems from the Literature Review.

Figure 8 is a wireframe made in Figma. It demonstrates what the user would see in the UI. Initially, the name of the website was called “WhaleWarden” with a red theme. This was later changed during Implementation. As you can see, there is a heuristic view of data with charting and a suitable sidebar and navbar navigation.

Figure 8 - "WhaleWarden" (Pre-WalletScan) Wireframe of Desktop UI Website (November 2023)

As per Figure 9, shows a wireframe of a DETAILED view of data. There are going to be users who wish to go more in depth of the aggregated data. As shown in Figure 9, as displayed by the rainbow-gradient showing a highlight, Downloading data as a CSV file or pulling more data could be possible for paying users not on a Free tier.

Figure 9 - Detailed View for advanced users

Detailed Swap Data
Analyse your scanned whales' trades below

Swaps | Held Tokens | Wallets | Indicators

Filter Swaps | View | Data | 5 Selected | Full Pricing Data | Download

Contract	Symbol	Name	Wallets	Agg. Quantity	Swap Direction	Agg. Supply %	New	Agg. \$ Value
0xfc312d2	PEPE	Pepe Coin X Reward	3	1,032,324,442,423.103	Buy	21.34%	Cross-Wallet	\$434,432,442
0xgh46x7	DOGE	Doge Meme III	1	3,565,243.402	Buy	0.46%	Individual	\$10,490
0xfc3g2d1	XDB	DigitalBits	9	10,000,023.203	Sell	10.45%		\$434,432,442
0xgfeu1111	YFDAl	YFDAl	8	403,201,12.203	Buy	1.23%	Cross-Wallet	\$434,432,442
0xfc312d2	STAR	Starlight Coin	4	1,102,200.304	Sell	0.56%		\$434,432,442
0xfc312d2	PEPE	Pepe Coin X Reward	3	1,032,324,442,423.103	Buy	21.34%	Cross-Wallet	\$434,432,442
0xgh46x7	DOGE	Doge Meme III	1	3,565,243.402	Buy	0.46%	Individual	\$10,490
0xfc3g2d1	XDB	DigitalBits	9	10,000,023.203	Sell	10.45%		\$434,432,442
0xgfeu1111	YFDAl	YFDAl	8	403,201,12.203	Buy	1.23%	Cross-Wallet	\$434,432,442
0xfc312d2	STAR	Starlight Coin	4	1,102,200.304	Sell	0.56%		\$434,432,442

0 of 100 row(s) selected. Rows per page: 10 Page 1 of 13

WORK IN PROGRESS

Below, in Figure 10, is a concept for the “WalletScan” Landing page. Although basic, it gets the point across. Most websites have a landing page that attracts users to the main app website.

Figure 10 - Landing Page Wireframe

Figure 11 - WhaleWarden Concept Dark

Figure 12 - WhaleWarden Concept 2 Info Dark

6. Implementation

6.1. Web3 Onboarding, Auth Flow & Security

The "Web3 Onboarding, Auth Flow & Security" stage of WalletScan involves a streamlined authentication process using Firebase Auth for both Google Sign-In and passwordless entry, emphasizing serverless execution directly on the client side. The process includes a welcome flow, beta access managed via Vercel KV, and secure wallet linking using WalletConnect with nonce cryptography to verify ownership. This setup efficiently prepares users for the application's tiered SaaS features.

6.1.1. Authentication

One of the first steps of the application was to allow users to sign in and do things, as with most web applications out there. Both Google Sign-In and Passwordless (email-only) auth was used. Below example is using Google Sign-In.

This was one of the major advantages towards the “Serverless” Approach since the majority of the Authentication logic has already been done – and the way to implement it goes against traditional serverful standards. Using Firebase Auth, a service part of Firebase, it allows a user to sign in to a website all from the client side, without interacting with any developer-made backend for a serverless-developer’s project (as displayed by *Figure 13*). The user directly interacts with Firebase servers. This applies to both signing up and signing in.

Figure 13 - Firebase Auth Client-Side Only Flow

Although this works for the client-side, and stores their ‘logged-in’ status in the browser securely – the backend (Next.js with App Router) does not have access to their login state.

For clarification, generally, Firebase is *meant* to be used *mostly* with client-side ONLY apps, however, due to the complex architecture of WalletScan, and the fact that due to security, some things have to be done on the backend – there needed to be some way to get access to the user’s details securely.

This is where a Session Token was used stored as a secure cookie in the browser of the user, passed along with every request.

After the user signed in client-side using Firebase Auth, an ID Token from Firebase was generated, which, when passed to the backend, can verify if the token is legitimate and *actually* from Firebase Auth and is valid (not banned user, etc) – then create a session token as per *Figure 14* and *Figure 15*

Figure 14 - Client-Side signIn() using Google Auth Firebase

```
walletscan - page.tsx

43  async function signIn(paginate: any) {
44    try {
45      const userCred = await signInWithPopup(auth, new GoogleAuthProvider());
46      // Sign in with Google popup using Firebase Auth and store the user creds in browser
47
48      const idToken = await userCred.user.getIdToken()
49      // Get the user's ID token so we can send it to the server for verification
50
51      const response = await fetch("/api/login", {
52        method: "POST",
53        cache: "no-store",
54        headers: {
55          Authorization: `Bearer ${idToken}`,
56        },
57      });
58
59
60      if (response.status === 200) {
61        // If the response status is 200, then the user has successfully logged in and/or
62        // been created on the backend and an async session token cookie has been created
63        // ...

```

Figure 15 - Backend API Route Handler for /login

```
walletscan - route.tsx

 9  export async function POST(request: NextRequest, response: NextResponse) {
10    const secure = process.env.NEXT_PUBLIC_LOGIN_DOMAIN !== "http://localhost:3000";
11    const authorization = headers().get("Authorization");
12    if (authorization?.startsWith("Bearer ")) {
13      const idToken = authorization.split("Bearer ")[1];
14      const decodedToken = await auth().verifyIdToken(idToken);
15
16      if (decodedToken) {
17        //Generate session cookie
18        const expiresIn = 60 * 60 * 24 * 5 * 1000;
19        const sessionCookie = await auth().createSessionCookie(idToken, {
20          expiresIn,
21        });
22        const options = {
23          name: "session",
24          value: sessionCookie,
25          maxAge: expiresIn,
26          httpOnly: true,
27          secure: secure
28        };
29
30        //Add the cookie to the browser
31        cookies().set(options);
32      }
33    }
34
35    return NextResponse.json({}, { status: 200 });
36  }
```

Below is the sign-up sign-in (2-in-1) page (<https://app.walletscan.io/login>) where a user would be redirected to from the Landing Page (<https://walletscan.io>). (Figure 16) (Figure 17)

Figure 16 - app.walletscan.io [Mobile]

The image shows a mobile login screen for WalletScan. The background is a dark gradient. At the top, the text "WalletScan" is displayed in white, followed by the tagline "Walk among wealth with the warriors". Below this is a text input field with the placeholder "Email Address" and "Enter your email". A blue button labeled "Continue with Email" is positioned below the input field. A horizontal line with the text "OR" in the center separates this from the next option. Below the line is a button with the Google logo and the text "Continue with Google".

Figure 17 - app.walletscan.io [Desktop]

The image shows a desktop login screen for WalletScan, which is a larger version of the mobile screen. It features the same layout: the "WalletScan" logo and tagline at the top, an email input field with the placeholder "Email Address" and "Enter your email", a blue "Continue with Email" button, a horizontal line with "OR" in the center, and a "Continue with Google" button with the Google logo at the bottom.

6.1.2. /Welcome Flow Redirect

After the user has signed up (first-time sign-up) they will be redirected to the /welcome route. The code to redirect is shown below, continuing on from Figure 14 code into Figure 18 (<https://app.walletscan.io/welcome>). By checking the 'isNewUser' attribute given from Firebase, a different flow can be given to the user.

If for any reason the user backs out of the /welcome flow and tries to sign in again, they will be redirected to the main page (<https://app.walletscan.io/>) which shows the dashboard – but due to the way the website has been made, user defaults will be set anyway, meaning even if the user exits the flow and doesn't give relevant info upon signing up, the user can still use the application without restriction - but at a level (Free Tier) unless they re-do the /welcome flow – so no mishandled errors there.

Figure 18 - Continuation of signIn() - Redirect Welcome

```
walletscan - page.tsx

60  if (response.status === 200) {
61      // If the response status is 200, then the user has successfully logged in and/or
62      // been created on the backend and an async session token cookie has been created
63      // ...
64
65      // get auth
66      const currentUser = auth.currentUser;
67
68      if (currentUser) {
69          const userId = currentUser.uid;
70
71          const additionalUserInfo = getAdditionalUserInfo(userCred);
72
73          if (additionalUserInfo?.isNewUser) {
74              router.push("/welcome");
75          }
76          else {
77              router.push("/");
78          }
79      }
80  }
81  }
82  else {
83      console.log('error')
84      toast.error("Error logging in. Please try again.");
85  }
```

The (animated) /welcome route page looks like so below. The “Get Started” button will show a non-loading enabled state after api is called to pull all relevant user information:

Figure 19 - /welcome

6.1.3. Beta Codes with Vercel KV

As most websites go through different stages of development, it made sense to simulate this by classifying WalletScan as a ‘Beta’ product (unfinished). A lot of video games (CheckpointGaming, 2023) and websites enter a ‘Closed Beta’ stage in which allows only certain selected individuals to use the website. WalletScan has this functionality by using Vercel KV (Vercel’s Key-Value Storage) (Vercel, n.d.) which “*is a durable Redis database that enables you to store and retrieve JSON data.*”. Redis is “*an open source, in-memory, NoSQL key/value store that is used primarily as an application cache or quick-response database*” (IBM, n.d.).

Vercel’s (Next.js-based) Middleware to intercept requests to check that, before any requests are made, a user has activated a unique Beta Code. If they don’t have one, they are redirected to the /welcome flow, otherwise, the request continues processing for execution as shown per *Figure 20*.

Figure 20 - Beta Code User Flow

For now, the beta code check is only done when the user goes to <https://app.walletscan.io> as per *Figure 21*.

Figure 21 - Middleware Beta Code Check

```
walletscan - middleware.ts
77  if (path === '/') {
78    if (isLoggedIn) {
79
80      console.log("checking beta code status")
81
82      const userId = decodedToken.uid;
83      const userBetaCode = await kv.get(userId + "_beta_code");
84      if (!userBetaCode || userBetaCode === null || userBetaCode === undefined) {
85        return NextResponse.redirect(request.nextUrl.origin + '/welcome');
86      }
87
88    }
89  }
```

The use of Beta Codes adds another layer of complexity to the application to show how malleable Serverless Technology can be as well as used, while also demonstrating the simulation of a real-world potential SaaS start-up website.

The beta codes are added manually via Vercel KV CLI on <https://vercel.com> as shown per *Figure 22*.

****If you want to access the website, below are some beta codes to use:**

- uni-beta-ny3c5sc4hz
- uni-beta-xy1c5scxhe
- uni-beta-1y2c53cxhe

Figure 22 - Vercel KV Storage CLI

The screenshot displays the Vercel KV Storage CLI interface for a database named "walletscan-kv". The interface includes a navigation bar with "All Databases" and "KV Database" options. The database status is "Available", and it is located in the "Washington, D.C., USA" region. The endpoint is "winning-swan-37257". The storage size is 29.8 kB, requests per month are 1k, and data transfer is 3.29 MB. A quickstart section provides a CLI command to connect to the database: `redis-cli --tls -u redis://*****:*****@winning-swan-37257.upstash.io:37257`. A larger window shows the CLI output, including a welcome message and several successful HSET commands:

```

Welcome to the KV CLI
+ HSET uni-beta-ktc85f0kc3 used "false" affiliation "Haynes" additional_info "CEO"
3
+ HSET uni-beta-q9hmtycd2i used "false" affiliation "Haynes" additional_info "CEO"
3
+ HSET uni-beta-gtkpcsjzfw used "false" affiliation "Haynes" additional_info "CEO"
3
+ HSET uni-beta-tjfy2eiy6w used "false" affiliation "Haynes" additional_info "CEO"

```

So – How does a user enter a beta code, and how does WalletScan verify it’s legitimacy to see if it exists and hasn’t been used already? As shown in *Figure 23* and *Figure 24*, the provided beta code from the user is checked and validated, and a state is set on their user id in Redis if beta code validation is okay. Either an error or success response will be returned to the user, either showing them an error on the client-side or allowing them to continue with the /welcome flow and access the site.

Figure 23 - Activate Beta Code API Route /activateBetaCode

```
walletscan - route.tsx
14 export async function POST(request: NextRequest, response: NextResponse) {
15   const originPath = request.nextUrl.origin
16
17   const user = await verifyToken(auth, request)
18   if (!user) {
19     return NextResponse.redirect(originPath + "/signup", { status: 302 })
20   }
21
22   const userId = user.uid;
23   const userBetaCode = await kv.get(userId + "_beta_code");
24
25   if (userBetaCode) {
26     return NextResponse.json({
27       error: "Code already activated."
28     }, { status: 401 });
29   }
30
31
32   let data;
33   try {
34     data = await request.json()
35   }
36   catch (error) {
37     return NextResponse.json({}, { status: 401 });
38   }
39
40   if (!data.code) {
41     return NextResponse.json({
42       error: "No beta code provided"
43     }, { status: 401 });
44   }
45
46   const betaCode = data.code;
47
48   const betaCodeUsed = await kv.hget("beta_code:" + betaCode, "used");
49   if (betaCodeUsed === "true" || betaCodeUsed === true) {
50     console.log("Beta code already used")
51     return NextResponse.json({
52       error: "Beta code already used"
53     }, { status: 401 });
54   }
55
56   if (betaCodeUsed === null || betaCodeUsed === undefined) {
57     return NextResponse.json({
58       error: "Invalid beta code. Possibly expired or incorrect"
59     }, { status: 401 });
60   }
61   // set beta code to used
62
63   await kv.hset("beta_code:" + betaCode, { used: "true" });
64   await kv.set(userId + "_beta_code", betaCode);
65
66   return NextResponse.json({ success: true }, { status: 200 });
67 }
```

Figure 24 - Activating Beta Code Flowchart

The designed Beta Code page of the /welcome flow looks as below (Figure 25) (Figure 26).

Figure 25 - Beta Code Input [Desktop]

Figure 26 - Beta Code Input [Mobile]

6.1.4. WalletConnect + Nonce Cryptography + Price Check

After the user has entered a valid beta code, the next part of the onboarding process involves the user connecting their web3 wallet to their website, linking said wallet to their user account. But why does the website do this? – The main reason is because, due to the ‘SaaS’ element, there has to be a way for the website to make money. The theoretical way was to create a custom ERC-20 utility token on the blockchain (like WalletScan’s own Stock, *as described in section 3.2*). The more supply the user holds in their connected wallet, the more features they have access to. The access to these features is delineated by three tiers. “Free”, “Pro” and “Whale”.

To achieve this, a package called “WalletConnect” was used. Specifically, the “Web3Modal” was used which easily provides React Hooks and a pre-designed Modal on the page which easily allows the user to connect their web3 wallet to the website. As per their website (WalletConnect, 2024), this is described specifically as “*a drop-in SDK to connect wallet users to your app, smoothly and securely*”. An example of initialising these Hooks is shown below (*Figure 27*) in which we use throughout the ConnectWalletPage (apart of the /welcome route page) to open the Modal, get their address, check if their wallet is connected already, etc.

Figure 27 - WalletConnect Web3Modal Hooks

```
walletscan - ConnectWalletPage.tsx
24  const { address, isConnecting, isDisconnected } = useAccount()
25  const { open } = useWeb3Modal()
```

As the website needs to ensure that the user adding a wallet *actually* owns the wallet, and not somebody else, a signature has to be made. (Arcana Network, 2023) “*Signing a transaction in Web3 involves using a private key to generate a digital signature. This signature proves that the transaction comes from a specific user without revealing their private key ... This is essential in a trustless environment like the blockchain, where transactions are irreversible and there is no central authority to resolve disputes.*”. The reason the website must verify that specific user has control of the wallet is since multiple Firebase User accounts should

NOT have the same wallet linked, due to the effects of the permissions (tier) system. If that was allowed, then a user could abuse and go over tier limits, as the tier limits are tied to the Firebase user, not the wallet address.

To ensure the signing is secure, a “nonce” is created initially when the user redirects to /welcome. *“In cryptography, a nonce is a one-time code selected in a random or pseudo-random manner that is used to securely transmit a main password, preventing replay attacks.”* (Brittany, 2024). The reason a nonce is generated is to prevent a replay attack and man-in-the-middle attacks. Since it’s a one-time code (included when signing as per *Figure 28*), that same signature cannot be generated again once, meaning if someone intercepted the request to get access to said signature, and re-used it, it wouldn’t be valid.

Figure 28 - handleSignMessage()

```
walletscan - ConnectWalletPage.tsx

26  const {
27    signMessage,
28    data: signature,
29    isSuccess,
30    isError,
31    error,
32  } = useSignMessage();
33
34
35  const handleSignMessage = async () => {
36    const message = "Please sign this message to confirm you own this wallet. " +
37      "We will only ask for this once. Your secret verification id is: " + welcomeData.nonce + ". " +
38      "Do not share this message with anyone.";
39
40    setIsAddingWallet(true);
41
42    try {
43      await signMessage({ message: message });
44    } catch (err) {
45      console.error('Error signing message:', err);
46    }
47  };
48  };
```

Once the user has signed the message and a signature has been created, the user will call an API route to add the wallet (passed with the signature in the body), and after signature verification, the wallet gets added.

The nonce creation API route is as shown per Figure 29, which uses random generation as well as the user ID to create it, and store the nonce in Vercel KV Storage with an expiry so it can then be checked in the add-wallet API route.

Figure 29 - Nonce creation API route logic

```
walletscan - route.tsx
12 export async function GET(request: NextRequest, response: NextResponse) {
13   const originPath = request.nextUrl.origin
14   const user = await verifyToken(auth, request)
15   if (!user) {
16     return NextResponse.redirect(originPath + "/signup", { status: 302 })
17   }
18
19   const randomNonceString = Math.random().toString(36).substring(2, 15)
20   + Math.random().toString(36).substring(2, 15);
21
22   const userId = user.uid;
23
24   const nonce = userId + "_" + randomNonceString;
25
26   await kv.set(userId + "_" + "nonce", nonce, { ex: 360 });
27
28   return NextResponse.json({ nonce: nonce }, { status: 200 });
29 }
```

After the wallet has been added, an initial balance check of the utility token (in this case, is USDT and not a custom WalletScan token) is retrieved using the QuickNode API. Retries are performed just in case the balance is zero (which did occur for unknown reasons during testing and debugging). This logic is shown as per Figure 30, which essentially pulls the utility token price from Vercel KV (for one token unit value), and then multiplies the price by the amount of tokens the user has in their connected wallet.

Figure 30 - Initial Balance Retrieval Logic

```

walletscan - route.tsx

163 let currentTokens = await core.client.qn_getWalletTokenBalance({
164     wallet: signingAddress,
165     contracts: [process.env.QUICKNODE_CONTRACT || ""]
166 });
167
168 let tokens = 0;
169
170 const result = currentTokens.result;
171 if (result.length > 0) {
172     const decimals = parseInt(result[0].decimals || "0");
173     // convert totalBalance to integer
174     const totalBalance = parseInt(result[0].totalBalance || "0");
175
176     if (decimals == 0 || totalBalance == 0) {
177         tokens = 0;
178     }
179     else {
180         tokens = totalBalance / Math.pow(10, decimals);
181     }
182 }
183 else {
184     for (let i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
185         console.log("Retrying to get tokens");
186         // wait 1 second before retrying
187
188         await new Promise(resolve => setTimeout(resolve, 500));
189         currentTokens = await core.client.qn_getWalletTokenBalance({
190             wallet: signingAddress,
191             contracts: [process.env.QUICKNODE_CONTRACT || ""]
192         });
193
194         if (currentTokens.result.length > 0) {
195             const decimals = parseInt(currentTokens.result[0].decimals || "0");
196             // convert totalBalance to integer
197             const totalBalance = parseInt(currentTokens.result[0].totalBalance || "0");
198
199             if (decimals == 0 || totalBalance == 0) {
200                 tokens = 0;
201             }
202             else {
203                 tokens = totalBalance / Math.pow(10, decimals);
204             }
205             break;
206         }
207     }
208 }
209
210 if (!currentTokens) {
211     return NextResponse.json({
212         error: "Failed to get tokens"
213     }, { status: 400 }); // Or an appropriate status code
214 }

```

Connecting a wallet on WalletScan looks like so in the below figures:

1. Before Connecting Wallet (*Figure 31*):

Figure 31 - Before Connecting Wallet on /welcome

2. "Connect Wallet" click opens WalletConnect modal (*Figure 32*):

Figure 32 - ConnectWallet Modal on /welcome

3. MetaMask Selection Button with WalletConnect Modal (Figure 33):

Figure 33 - MetaMask Popup after Web3Modal Selection /welcome

4. After Connecting Wallet by confirming in MetaMask (Figure 34):

Figure 34 - After Connecting Wallet on /welcome

5. After Clicking ‘Verify Ownership’ button, opening MetaMask signing page (*Figure 35*):

Figure 35 - MetaMask Signature Popup Page

6. After successful signature request confirming ownership of wallet (*Figure 36*) going to Tier Selection Page:

Figure 36 - /welcome tiers page

6.1.5. Pricing Page and Final Page

Due to WalletScan being classed as a SaaS – there are multiple tiers, permissions and features that the user will have access to depending on the amount of supply of the utility token they hold. If the amount they hold is equivalent to or over the USD value of the suggested tiers, they will have access to them features. Each tier card has a ‘Buy with Uniswap’ button. This button leads to a DEX where, theoretically, they could purchase the utility token if desired – however, due to that being out of scope of the dissertation, there is no utility token – currently only USDT is used for testing. The tiers are below in *Figure 37*:

Figure 37 - WalletScan SaaS Tiers

The screenshot displays the 'Pricing' page for WalletScan. At the top, it states 'To use WalletScan, you need to hold \$SCAN tokens in your wallet.' and shows 'Your Total Balance: \$0.00 SCAN'. Below this, there are three pricing tiers:

- Free:** For starters that want to try out the platform. Features include: Scan 1 primary wallet, 5 scans per month, and Basic Scan Features. A 'Continue with Free' button is at the bottom.
- Pro:** Access exclusive paid features & more scannable wallets. Price is \$49 held in wallet. Features include: Scan up to 50 wallets, 40 scans per month, Basic & Premium Scan Features, CSV & JSON Export, Access to WalletScan Prestige, and 1 Raffle Entry per month. A 'Buy with Uniswap' button is at the bottom.
- Whale:** For whales that want the best of the best, and more. Price is \$149 held in wallet. Features include: Scan up to 200 wallets, 150 scans per month, Basic, Premium & Whale Scan Features, Access to SmartWhale Finder, Telegram Bot Integration, CSV & JSON Export, Daily Auto-Scan, VIP Telegram Group Access, Access to WalletScan Prestige, and 4 Raffle Entries per month. A 'Buy with Uniswap' button is at the bottom.

After the user clicks the tier they decide to continue with, they will be shown the final page which launches a Confetti effect when loaded on the /welcome route showing they completed setup, and they can click the “Open WalletScan” button to go to the dashboard at <https://app.walletscan.io>. The page looks as below in *Figure 38*:

Figure 38 - Final Welcome Page

The Confetti is implemented using a third-party package called ‘react-confetti’ like so in :

```
walletscan - FinalPage.tsx

29 const [width, setWidth] = useState(0);
30 const [height, setHeight] = useState(0);
31
32 useEffect(() => {
33   setWidth(window.innerWidth);
34   setHeight(window.innerHeight);
35 }, []);
36
37
38
39 return (
40
41   <div className='flex h-screen flex-col w-full items-center justify-center'>
42
43     <Confetti
44       width={width}
45       height={height}
46       className="flex mt-[-50px]"
47       run={true}
48       // numberOfPieces={300}
49       // tweenDuration={5000}
50       recycle={false} />

```

6.2. WalletScan Dashboard

Below are the final designs on the WalletScan Dashboard for Mobile and Desktop. These designs were changed multiple times throughout development to get it in to a position that is not only responsive, but looks good while also highlighting the “WalletScan” brand.

The dashboard relies on Next.js layouts, NextUI, NextUI Pro, TailwindCSS, etc.

Figure 39 - WalletScan [Desktop]

The Desktop design is dynamic and changes what is shown in the main content as well as the sidebar (and navbar for mobile) depending on what scans, wallets, etc they have created in the database. As per *Figure 39*, a message is shown to the user to ‘Add Wallets’ as they haven’t added any yet (due to being a first-time user) – but if the user has scans or wallets, etc, the content will change through client-side React/Next.js code.

Figure 40 - WalletScan [Mobile]

On mobile, since the viewport is a lot smaller, a minimal navbar is shown with the option to hide or show the sidebar responsively. *Figure 40* shows the sidebar hidden, whereas *Figure 41* shows it open.

Figure 41 - WalletScan Sidebar Open [Mobile]

6.3. Adding Wallets

Before a user can scan any wallets for data, they have to add wallets first.

At the <https://app.walletscan.io/wallets> route, users can add wallets one-by-one. Initially, it was planned that after the user connects their wallet (via browser with web3 to establish their user tier and permissions), the website would launch async tasks to analyse the wallets to see what *other* wallets were interacted with. These *other* wallets would automatically be added just purely to fill up space and show how advanced / smart the application is. There was also plans to allow for CSV Imports of Wallets to make it faster for a user, as well as an 'AI Copy & Paste' functionality which would use an LLM (OpenAI API) to automatically add wallets even if the pasted text or image of wallets text is not structured. Unfortunately, due to time constraints, these features were not implemented. For now, a simple responsive Modal is used to allow the user to add a wallet as well as add 'Tags' to it, which allow for easy grouping and organisation of wallets. Multiple wallets could have the same tag. Multiple wallets can have multiple tags per wallet.

Below is what the /wallets route looks like, giving the user the option to filter and 'Add Wallet' (Figure 42).

Figure 42 - /wallets route

Below is the ‘Add Wallet’ modal that opens to allow a wallet to be added and scanned later (Figure 43)

Figure 43 - Add Wallet (empty) modal

When the wallet address is entered, a client-side API request will be made to a Cloudflare JSON RPC Provider which checks to see if there is an “ENS Name” attached to the wallet. If there is, then it automatically fills in the optional “Wallet Name” field.

The code uses a ‘lookupAddress’ function to do this as per Figure 44.

Figure 44 - `getENSName()` function

```
walletscan - getEnsName.tsx
1  const getEnsName = async (address: string,
2    setIsEnsLoading: (isLoading: boolean) => void,
3    setEnsNames: (ensNames: any) => void,
4    ethersProvider: any,
5    ensNames: any
6
7  ) => {
8
9    const lowercaseAddress = address.toLowerCase().trim()
10
11    if (ensNames[lowercaseAddress]) {
12      return ensNames[lowercaseAddress]
13    }
14    try {
15      setIsEnsLoading(true)
16      const ensName = await ethersProvider.lookupAddress(lowercaseAddress)
17      console.log(ensName)
18
19      setEnsNames((ensNames: any) => {
20        return {
21          ...ensNames,
22          [lowercaseAddress]: ensName
23        }
24      })
25
26      setIsEnsLoading(false)
27      return ensName
28    } catch (error) {
29
30      console.error(error)
31      setEnsNames((ensNames: any) => {
32        return {
33          ...ensNames,
34          [lowercaseAddress]: ''
35        }
36      })
37      setIsEnsLoading(false)
38      return ''
39    }
40  }
```

When the wallet details are filled in, and tags are made, the user can now add the wallet. When the user clicks the “Add Wallet” button, the ‘POST’ `/api/wallets` route is called with the user info and wallet info, and validation is done to ensure the wallet is a legitimate address in the backend as well as front-end. An example of some filled out valid wallet details is shown in *Figure 45*.

Figure 45 - Add Wallet (Valid Details)

Once a wallet is added, the user has the ability to EDIT (PUT) or DELETE wallets as shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46 - /wallets with wallets

In the POST route, wallets are validated and checked. Using Firestore, the wallet is stored – but in an untraditional way. Since Firestore has read/write costs, it made sense to store the wallet in one big document in an array where all the other wallets are stored. This allows for less read costs to be incurred and the ability to pull all wallets in one database query. If there was a very large amount of wallets that could be stored per user, this approach wouldn't work scale well, but since the max is around 300, it made sense to do it this way. This is displayed in *Figure 47* when dealing with the 'walletDoc'.

Figure 47 - POST /wallets section

```
walletscan - route.tsx

206 const [isValid, message, cleanedData] = await validateWallet(data)
207   if (!isValid) {
208     return NextResponse.json({ message: message }, { status: 400 });
209   }
210
211   const firestore = getFirestore();
212
213   cleanedData.updatedAt = Timestamp.fromDate(new Date());
214   cleanedData.createdAt = Timestamp.fromDate(new Date());
215
216   const walletDocRef = firestore.collection('wallets').doc(user.uid);
217   const walletDoc = await walletDocRef.get();
218
219   if (!walletDoc.exists) {
220     await walletDocRef.set({
221       wallets: [cleanedData]
222     });
223   }
224   else {
225     const walletData = walletDoc.data();
226     if (walletData) {
227       const walletArray: WalletType[] = walletData.wallets;
228
229       // Check if wallet already exists
230       const walletExists = walletArray.some((wallet) => wallet.address === cleanedData.address);
231       if (walletExists) {
232         return NextResponse.json({ message: "Wallet already exists" }, { status: 400 });
233       }
234
235       walletArray.push(cleanedData);
236       await walletDocRef.update({
237         wallets: walletArray
238       });
239     }
240   }
241
242
243   return NextResponse.json({
244     message: "Wallet added successfully",
245     data: cleanedData
246   }, { status: 200 });
```

6.4. Creating a Scan

Creating a Scan to find, aggregate and deal with wallet data was the hardest challenge of the entire dissertation. Scaling the process and ensuring fast speeds by abiding by third-party rate limits was a monolith of a task to complete successfully. This subsection will go through the flow, process, steps, problems, and overall workings of how a “WalletScan” is made.

6.4.1. Scan Workflow Diagram

The most difficult part of the dissertation was creating a scalable workflow (using serverless resources) to scan wallets. In *Figure 48*, a detailed overview of the entire architecture and workflow is shown, and explained later in the further subsections.

Figure 48 - Scan Workflow

6.4.2. Scan Initial Setup

To start off, below are the scan setup pages (/create-scan) that is essentially a setup wizard guiding the user on how to create a scan. After the user has added their wallets and presses “New Scan” on the dashboard page, they will be redirected to <https://app.walletscan.io/create-scan> which is shown in *Figure 49*.

Figure 49 - /create-scan welcome page

Next, the user will choose the wallets they wish to scan. Based on the tier they're on, they will only be allowed to select a certain amount of wallets for scanning. The responsive table (made using NextUI and custom tailwind css) is shown below in *Figure 50*.

Figure 50 - Scan Setup - Select Wallets

Based on the amount of wallets the user selects as well as the user's tier, it will show certain "Scan Features" the user can select. These features are the types of data that gets aggregated and shown to the user in the final scan. In *Figure 51*, two features are shown for selection.

Figure 51 - Scan Setup - Feature Select

Lastly, after showing the user an overview as per *Figure 52*, they would then click the animated rainbow gradient “Scan” button, which starts a largely complicated chain of events to get the scan completed. While the scan is being ran, the user is shown dynamic UI skeletons to indicate that the scan is loading and the user should wait as shown in *Figure 53*. A skeleton is “*is a visual placeholder that appears before the page content renders completely.*” (Juviler, 2024).

Figure 52 - Scan Setup - Confirm Scan

Figure 53 - Scan Creation - Loading Skeletons

6.4.3. Scan Creation Entrypoint

After the user presses “Scan” and has their wallets and features selected, the first request with the mentioned data is sent to “/api/scans” which is a Vercel Serverless Function.

1. Within the Serverless Function, the user’s wallets, the amount of scans they have left, and the features selected are all validated beforehand.
2. After validation, the scan documents are created in Firestore (first) and in the Realtime Database (second, using the Firestore Doc ID for tracking). For cleaning-up purposes, the scanCreatedTime is added so the CRON job, later, can delete old data in Realtime Database. The reason Realtime Database is used is because of pricing, as read/write counts do not matter unlike Firestore, and since there are a lot of read/writes, it made sense use it. Realtime Database charges by the amount of storage, that’s why it has to be deleted. Creation is shown as per *Figure 54*.

Figure 54 - Scan Creation Code

A screenshot of a code editor showing the implementation of the scan creation endpoint. The code is written in TypeScript and uses the Firebase SDK for Firestore and Realtime Database. It starts by creating a Firestore document reference for the 'scans' collection, then uses that ID to create a reference in the Realtime Database. The Realtime Database document is then set with the scan ID, user ID, and cleaned wallet data. Finally, a reference to the Realtime Database document is created for tracking scan creation times, and it is set with the current date and time.

```
walletscan - route.tsx

399 const scanDocRef = firestore.collection('scans').doc();
400 const scanId = scanDocRef.id;
401
402 // Create the scan in the realtime database:
403 const scanRef = database.ref(`scans/${scanId}`);
404 await scanRef.set({
405   id: scanId,
406   userId: user.uid,
407   wallets: cleanedData.wallets,
408 });
409
410 const scanTimeCreatedRef = database.ref(`scansCreatedTimes/${scanId}`)
411 await scanTimeCreatedRef.set(`${Date.now()}`);
```

3. After the documents for scans are created, a map of Features (the datapoints the scan aggregates) are added to the firestore document as well as the realtime database document which allows for tracking throughout the scan, setting statuses, allowing the backend to know when and when not to merge aggregation results, etc. Some features

need ‘preprocessing checks’ on the wallets to ensure, during the main aggregation / analysis stage, it doesn’t fail. The functionality is shown in *Figure 55*.

Figure 55 - Setting FeatureMap

```
walletscan - route.tsx
426 const featuresMap = {};
427
428 for (const featureId of cleanedData.features) {
429   const checks: { [key: string]: any } = {};
430   if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
431     checks["checkWalletTokenCount"] = {
432       status: "pending",
433       checkCalls: {}
434     };
435   }
436
437   if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
438
439     for (let i = 0; i < cleanedDataChunks.length; i++) {
440       const checkCallId = `checkCall${i + 1}`;
441       checks["checkWalletTokenCount"].checkCalls[checkCallId] = {
442         status: "pending"
443       }
444     }
445
446     (featuresMap as { [key: string]: any })[featureId] = {
447       featureId,
448       featureName: featureId,
449       preprocessing: {
450         status: "pending",
451         checks: checks
452       }
453     }
454   }
455
456   if (featureId === "WalletTokensAndPrices") {
457     (featuresMap as { [key: string]: any })[featureId] = {
458       featureId,
459       featureName: featureId,
460       preprocessing: {
461         status: "success",
462         checks: {}
463       }
464     }
465   }
466 }
467
468 // set the features in the realtime database
469 await database.ref(`scans/${scanId}/features`).set(featuresMap);
470
471 const features = Object.keys(featuresMap);
472 const featuresUpdate: { [key: string]: any } = {};
473
474 // Construct the features object
475 for (const featureId of features) {
476   featuresUpdate[featureId] = {
477     featureId: featureId,
478     status: "pending",
479   };
480 }
481
482 // Perform a single write to Firestore
483 await scanDocRef.set({
484   features: featuresUpdate,
485   totalFeatures: features.length,
486   createdAt: FieldValue.serverTimestamp(),
487   featuresCompleted: {
488
489   },
490   userId: user.uid,
491 }, { merge: true });
```

4. Depending on each feature, the next part is to perform actions that start the processing of each feature. In *Figure 56* below, SharedHeldTokensCount and WalletTokensAndPrices are launched differently. Since SharedHeldTokensCount requires preprocessing checks before the actual aggregation scan, tasks are launched to the Google Tasks Queue, and WalletTokensAndPrices has an update on statuses on the Realtime Database which triggers a Firebase Function Trigger to start the analysis conditionally. The Tasks Queue and Firebase Function Trigger functionality is explained in later subsections.

Figure 56 - Feature Start

```

walletscan - route.tsx
499 for (const [featureId, feature] of Object.entries(featuresMap)) {
500   if (featureId === "WalletTokensAndPrices") {
501     await database.ref(`scans/${scanId}/features/${featureId}`).update({
502       preprocessing: {
503         status: "pending",
504         message: "No preprocessing required for this feature."
505       },
506       analysis: {
507         status: "pending",
508         message: "Currently pending for analysis"
509       }
510     });
511   }
512
513   if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
514     const checks = (feature as { [key: string]: any }).preprocessing.checks;
515     for (const [checkType, check] of Object.entries(checks)) {
516       const checkCalls = (check as { [key: string]: any }).checkCalls;
517       for (const [checkCallId, checkCall] of Object.entries(checkCalls)) {
518         const payload = {
519           userId: user.uid,
520           featureId: featureId,
521           scanId: scanId,
522           checkType: checkType,
523           checkId: checkType,
524           checkParams: {
525             wallet_addresses: cleanedDataChunks[Number(checkCallId.split("checkCall")[1]) - 1],
526             blockchain: "ethereum"
527           },
528           checkCallId: checkCallId
529         };
530
531         const taskConfig = {
532           task: {
533             httpRequest: {
534               httpMethod: 'POST',
535               url: process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_CHECK_CALL_URL,
536               headers: {
537                 'Content-Type': 'application/json',
538               },
539             },
540             oidcToken: {
541               serviceAccountEmail: process.env.GOOGLE_CLIENT_EMAIL,
542               audience: process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_CHECK_CALL_URL,
543             },
544             body: Buffer.from(JSON.stringify(payload)).toString('base64'),
545           }
546         };
547
548         // Send the task to Google Cloud Tasks
549         const response = await fetch(url, {
550           method: 'POST',
551           headers: {
552             'Authorization': `Bearer ${accessToken.token}`,
553             'Accept': 'application/json',
554             'Content-Type': 'application/json',
555           },
556           body: JSON.stringify(taskConfig),
557         });
558
559         const responseData = await response.json();
560
561         if (!response.ok) {
562           // update the feature in the realtime database with the error message
563           await database.ref(`scans/${scanId}/features/${featureId}/preprocessing`).update({
564             status: "fail",
565             message: responseData.error.message
566           });
567
568           // update firestore for specific feature with the error message
569
570           await scanDocRef.set({
571             features: {
572               [featureId]: {
573                 status: "fail",
574                 message: responseData.error.message
575               }
576             }, { merge: true });
577
578         }
579         else {
580           console.log("response ok")
581           console.log('responseData', responseData)
582         }
583       }
584     }
585   }
586 }
587
588
589 }
590 }

```

5. Lastly, after launching the scan, the user's scan counter is increased in Vercel KV as per Figure 57

Figure 57 - Update Scan Counter

```
walletscan - route.tsx

593 // update the user's scan counter
594
595   if (scanCounterType === "rewards") {
596     const updatedScans = await kv.decr(user.uid + "_reward_scans");
597
598     return NextResponse.json({
599       message: "Scan created successfully",
600       scanId: scanId,
601       updatedScans: updatedScans,
602       scanCounterType: scanCounterType,
603     }, { status: 200 });
604   }
605   else {
606     const updatedScans = await kv.incr(user.uid + "_scans_" + monthYearString);
607
608     return NextResponse.json({
609       message: "Scan created successfully",
610       scanId: scanId,
611       updatedScans: updatedScans,
612       scanCounterType: scanCounterType,
613     }, { status: 200 });
614   }
```

6.4.4. Triggers, Synchronicity, APIs & Queues

Figure 58 - Subsection of Architecture for Scanning

Below is a detailed explanation of the above flow shown in *Figure 58*:

One of the most important aspects of the scan architecture is ensuring that features are aggregated and dealt with concurrently with great performance. One of the huge benefits of using a serverless cloud like Firebase is their Firebase Triggers. “*Cloud Firestore triggers allow you to execute code whenever a document is written, created, updated, or deleted.*” (Dev, 2020). Due to this functionality, it allows for synchronous actions to be performed in an asynchronous environment.

Since preconditions occur for scan features, such as ‘checks’ for the SharedHeldTokensCount feature (as mentioned in the previous section), some functions must run at certain points throughout the scan based on certain conditions, hence the ‘synchronous’ aspect. In regard to

the ‘asynchronous’ classification of the scanning process – the fact that trigger functions, feature API calls, other cloud functions and cross-feature aggregation in general, can all run in parallel without a lot of ‘blocking’ occurring ensures efficiency and optimisation – while still running certain actions on scan features in a synchronous way (per-feature synchronicity basically).

Another big scenario is when multiple API calls are made to the blockchain aggregation service (known as Transpose.io) for one feature. The results of these API requests (responses with blockchain data) need to be *further* aggregated *only when* all the API calls have been made and stored in Vercel KV. Although these API calls can be made at the same time concurrently, the architecture needs to wait until all are completed for this ‘final aggregation’ can happen, hence the synchronicity.

This functionality is achieved through tracking the state of the realtime database scan document’s feature’s statuses. As a Trigger is set off by a change in state on the database (based on certain rules), certain conditions and code in the trigger function can control the entire scan’s actions.

The change in state occurs in the ‘transposeCall’ and ‘checkCall’ Google Cloud Functions. The purpose of the ‘transposeCall’ function is to make the API call to ‘Transpose.io’ which gets the blockchain data in an aggregated format, store that data in Vercel KV (for later to be further aggregated and retrieved in the Firebase Trigger Function), and then change the realtime database scan document feature state, thus causing the Firebase Function Trigger to trigger and run. The same occurs for the ‘checkCall’ except it’s used for seeing whether a scan should run or not based on the wallets’ data the user has decided to scan.

These Google Cloud Functions (not Firebase Functions) are executed when the Google Task Queue says so. *“Cloud Tasks is a fully managed service that allows you to manage the execution, dispatch, and delivery of a large number of distributed tasks. Using Cloud Tasks, you can perform work asynchronously outside of a user or service-to-service request.”* (Google, 2024). The reason for using a distributed queue is due to the fact that the Transpose.io API (and potentially other ones in the future) have a Rate Limit of 1 request per second on the Free Tier. *“Rate limiting is a technique used to control the rate at which requests are made to a network, server, or other resource. It is used to prevent excessive or*

abusive use of a resource and to ensure that the resource is available to all users.” (Ghosh, 2023). The queue set up abides by these rules.

Code Samples & Explanations

Due to the large complexity of the process as well as the max word count, only a few key examples of code demonstrating the flow and scan process are mentioned below.

Subsection of Firebase Trigger Checking Conditions (Figure 59)

One of the biggest problems with the trigger was to not cause any infinite loops. Since, sometimes, during analysis checks and different parts of the trigger, state would be set in the database on the same document, it would trigger the Trigger again, resulting in an infinite loop. This was solved by adding conditional statements based on the statuses stored as shown. ‘afterData’ is the, changed state.

Figure 59 - RT DB Trigger Subsection

```

walletscan - index.js
929 exports.onFeatureRealtimeUpdate = functions.database.ref('/scans/{scanId}/features/{featureId}')
930 .onUpdate(async (change, context) => {
931   const kv = createClient({ url: process.env.KV_REST_API_URL, token: process.env.KV_REST_API_TOKEN });
932   const client = await authObj.getClient();
933   const accessToken = await client.getAccessToken();
934   const { scanId, featureId } = context.params;
935   const afterData = await change.after.val();
936
937   console.log("Scan ID:", scanId, "Feature ID:", featureId, "After Data:", afterData);
938
939   if (afterData.preprocessing.status === 'fail') return null;
940
941   if (afterData.preprocessing.status === 'success') {
942     let failedWallets = [];
943
944     if (!afterData.analysis) {
945       console.log("Analysis is undefined");
946       return null;
947     }
948
949     if (afterData.analysis.status === 'success' || afterData.analysis.status === 'fail') {
950       console.log("Analysis status is success or fail");
951       return null;
952     }
953
954     let analysingStatus = 'pending'
955
956     if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
957       analysingStatus = await determineAnalysisStatus(afterData);
958     }
959     else if (featureId === "WalletTokensAndPrices") {
960       if (afterData.analysis.featureCalls) {
961         const analysingInfo = await determineAnalysisStatusWalletTokensAndPrices(afterData);
962         failedWallets = analysingInfo.failedWallets;
963         analysingStatus = analysingInfo.status;
964       }
965     }
966     else {
967       analysingStatus = 'pending'
968     }
969   }
970
971   if (analysingStatus === 'success' && afterData.analysis.status !== analysingStatus) {
972     // ...
973
974
975
976
977

```

Queue Setup YAML & Task Dispatching

In *Figure 60* is the code that gets deployed to Google Tasks to setup the queue with a rate limit of 1 per second, abiding by Transpose.io's rate limits. To deploy, after signing in with Google Cloud, the command shown in *Figure 61* is used.

Figure 60 - Google Task Queue YAML Setup

A screenshot of a terminal window with a dark background. At the top, there are three colored circles (red, yellow, green) followed by the text 'walletscan - queue.yaml'. Below this, the contents of the YAML file are displayed with line numbers from 1 to 8. The code is as follows:

```
1 queue:
2   - name: TranposeQ
3     rate: 1/s
4     bucket_size: 1
5     max_concurrent_requests: 1
6     retry_parameters:
7       task_retry_limit: 0
8
```

Figure 61 - Deploy Task Queue Command

A screenshot of a terminal window with a dark background. It shows two lines of code: the first line is 'base ~/walletscan/walletscan git:(main)' and the second line is 'gcloud app --location europe-west2 deploy queue.yaml'.

```
base ~/walletscan/walletscan git:(main)
gcloud app --location europe-west2 deploy queue.yaml
```

The resulting outcome after deployment displays the queue on the Google Cloud Tasks website (*Figure 62*).

Figure 62 - Cloud Tasks Dashboard

The screenshot shows the Google Cloud Tasks dashboard for a queue named 'TranposeQ'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Google Cloud logo, a dropdown menu for 'WalletScan', and a search bar. Below the navigation bar, there are several action buttons: 'Queue details', 'REFRESH', 'EDIT QUEUE', 'PAUSE QUEUE', and 'DELETE QUEUE'. The main content area shows the queue name 'TranposeQ' with a green checkmark and an upward arrow. Below this, there is a table with three columns: 'Location', 'Type', and 'Tasks in queue'. The table contains one row with the following values: 'Location: europe-west2', 'Type: Push', and 'Tasks in queue: 0'. Below the table, there are four tabs: 'METRICS', 'LOGS', 'TASKS', and 'CONFIGURATION'. The 'CONFIGURATION' tab is selected and highlighted. Under the 'CONFIGURATION' tab, there are three sections: 'Location', 'Rate limits', and 'Retry parameters'. Each section contains a table of configuration values.

Location	Type	Tasks in queue
europe-west2	Push	0

Location	
Location	europe-west2

Rate limits	
Max rate	1/s
Max concurrent	1
Max burst size	1

Retry parameters	
Max attempts	1
Min interval	0.100s
Max interval	3600s
Max doublings	16
Max retry duration	Unlimited

Pushing a task to the queue is done by making a request to the cloud tasks API which references a specific Google Cloud Function to be run. In *Figure 63* below, multiple tasks are launched in a for loop for the 'SharedHeldTokensCount' feature. Environment variables are used for the Function URLs as development functions can differ from production functions.

Figure 63 - Task Launching Example

```

walletscan - index.js
239 const project = process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_PROJECT_ID;
240 const location = process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_LOCATION;
241 const queue = 'TranposeQ';
242
243 const url = `https://cloudtasks.googleapis.com/v2beta3/projects/${project}/locations/${location}/queues/${queue}/tasks`;
244
245 if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
246   let analysingMap = {};
247   chunks.forEach((chunk, index) => {
248     analysingMap[`SharedHeldTokensCountCall${index + 1}`] = {
249       status: 'pending',
250       wallets: chunk,
251     };
252   });
253
254   // console.log("Analysing map:", analysingMap);
255
256   await admin.database().ref(`/scans/${scanId}/features/${featureId}/analysis`).set({
257     status: 'pending',
258     featureCalls: analysingMap,
259   });
260
261   const tasksToExecute = [];
262
263   for (let index = 0; index < chunks.length; index++) {
264     const chunk = chunks[index];
265     const featureCallId = `SharedHeldTokensCountCall${index + 1}`;
266
267     const updatedPayload = {
268       userId: afterData.userId,
269       featureId: featureId,
270       scanId: scanId,
271       featureCallId: featureCallId,
272       callMode: callMode,
273       wallet_addresses: chunk,
274       blockchain: "ethereum",
275     };
276
277
278
279     const taskConfig = {
280       task: {
281         httpRequest: {
282           httpMethod: 'POST',
283           url: process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_TRANSPOSE_CALL_URL,
284           headers: {
285             'Content-Type': 'application/json',
286           },
287           oidcToken: {
288             serviceAccountEmail: process.env.GOOGLE_CLIENT_EMAIL,
289             audience: process.env.GOOGLE_TASK_TRANSPOSE_CALL_URL,
290           },
291           body: Buffer.from(JSON.stringify(updatedPayload)).toString('base64'),
292         }
293       }
294     };
295
296     tasksToExecute.push(
297       {
298         url: url,
299         taskConfig: taskConfig,
300         accessToken: accessToken,
301       }
302     )
303   }
304
305   for (let i = 0; i < tasksToExecute.length; i++) {
306     const task = tasksToExecute[i];
307     const response = await fetch(task.url, {
308       method: 'POST',
309       headers: {
310         'Authorization': `Bearer ${task.accessToken.token}`,
311         'Accept': 'application/json',
312         'Content-Type': 'application/json',
313       },
314       body: JSON.stringify(task.taskConfig),
315     });
316   }

```

Transpose API Call (Google Cloud Function ran from Task Queue)

In *Figure 64* is a subsection of the transposeCall GCloud Function. As each Feature has different parameters a map was defined with the function to call to get the resulting aggregated blockchain data from Transpose. After the data has been retrieved, or failed, a resulting status will be set and the data will be stored in Vercel KV. The reason it is not stored in Realtime Database is due to the large size of the data which caused errors during development.

Figure 64 - transposeCall subsection

```
walletscan - index.js
137 if (featureId === 'SharedHeldTokensCount' ) {
138
139   featureParams = {
140     blockchain: chain,
141     wallet_addresses: wallet_addresses,
142     callMode: callMode,
143   };
144
145 }
146
147 if (featureId === 'WalletTokensAndPrices' ) {
148
149   featureParams = {
150     blockchain: chain,
151     wallet_address: wallet_addresses[0],
152     callMode: callMode,
153   };
154 }
155
156
157 const featureFunctionsList = featureFunctions.featureFunctions
158
159
160 const featureFunction = featureFunctionsList[featureId];
161
162 const featuresRef = database.ref(`scans/${scanId}/features/${featureId}`);
163
164 // Call the check function
165
166 let result; // Declare data outside the try-catch block
167 try {
168   result = await featureFunction(featureParams);
169
170   await featuresRef.child(`analysis/featureCalls/${featureCallId}`).update({
171     status: result.status,
172   });
173
174   kv.set(`${scanId}-${featureId}-${featureCallId}`, JSON.stringify(result), { ex: 3600 });
175
176   return res.status(200).send(result);
177
178
179 } catch (error) {
180   console.log(error);
181
182
183   // Update the status of the check in the database without overwriting the other fields
184   await featuresRef.child(`analysis/featureCalls/${featureCallId}`).update({
185     status: 'fail',
186     message: error.toString() || 'An unknown error occurred'
187   });
188
189   return res.status(500).send(error.toString());
190 }
```

On Transpose.io playground website, PostgreSQL queries were made to retrieve and aggregate wallet data. An example and outline of the playground site is shown below in *Figure 65*.

Figure 65 - Transpose.io Playground

The screenshot shows the Transpose.io Playground website interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'Documentation', 'Atlas', and 'Playground', along with a 'PostgreSQL for SharedHeldTokensCount feature' title and an 'Upgrade' button. The main area is divided into two panels. On the left, under 'My Queries', there is a search bar and a list of saved queries, including 'Scratch Query', 'WalletScan', and 'SharedHeldTokensCountChunks'. On the right, a code editor displays a PostgreSQL query for 'SharedHeldTokensCountChunks'. The query uses a CTE to calculate wallet counts and then joins it with token data. A red arrow points to the 'Deploy' button, with a note: 'Button to create API url to call in transposeCall'.

```

1  WITH shared_tokens_counts AS (
2    SELECT
3      contract_address,
4      COUNT(DISTINCT owner_address) AS wallet_count
5    FROM
6      {{blockchain}}.token_owners
7    WHERE
8      owner_address IN ({{wallet_addresses}})
9    GROUP BY
10     contract_address
11  )
12
13  SELECT
14    stc.contract_address,
15    t.name AS token_name,
16    stc.wallet_count,
17    t.symbol AS token_symbol,
18    t.image_url AS token_image_url,
19    t.verified as token_verified
20  FROM
21    shared_tokens_counts stc
22  JOIN
23    {{blockchain}}.tokens t ON stc.contract_address = t.contract_address
24  ORDER BY
25    stc.wallet_count DESC;

```

Trigger Final Aggregation Store & Sharding

After all the transpose calls are made and results are stored in KV Storage for a feature, that feature's entire data would then have a last aggregation stage where the results are merged and stored in Firestore as 'featureScan' documents for fast access from the user.

As each feature is different and has different data, the aggregation works differently for each one.

As shown in *Figure 66*, featureScan documents are set with the data retrieved from each feature function aggregation and statuses are updated in a batch for efficiency. Since Firestore

has a 1MB document size limit, sharding is also in place to spread data over multiple documents to overcome this limitation.

Figure 66 - Final Aggregation on Features

```
walletscan - index.js
972 if (analysingStatus === 'success' && afterData.analysis.status !== analysingStatus) {
973   // ...
974   let aggregatedFeatureScans = [];
975   if (featureId === "SharedHeldTokensCount") {
976     console.log("Aggregating data for SharedHeldTokensCount");
977     aggregatedFeatureScans = await aggregateDataSharedHeldTokensCount(afterData.analysis.featureCalls, scanId, featureId, kv);
978   }
979
980   if (featureId === "WalletTokensAndPrices") {
981     console.log("Aggregating data for WalletTokensAndPrices");
982     aggregatedFeatureScans = await aggregateDataWalletTokensAndPrices(afterData.analysis.featureCalls, scanId, featureId, kv);
983   }
984 }
985
986 let batch = admin.firestore().batch();
987
988 for (let i = 0; i < aggregatedFeatureScans.length; i++) {
989   const chunk = aggregatedFeatureScans[i];
990   const featureScanRef = admin.firestore().collection("featureScans").doc();
991   batch.set(featureScanRef, {
992     featureScanId: featureScanRef.id,
993     scanId,
994     featureId,
995     shardIndex: i,
996     totalChunks: aggregatedFeatureScans.length,
997     data: chunk
998   }, { ignoreUndefinedProperties: true });
999 }
1000
1001 const scanRef = admin.firestore().collection("scans").doc(scanId);
1002
1003 batch.set(scanRef, {
1004   features: {
1005     [featureId]: {
1006       status: 'success',
1007       updatedAt: admin.firestore.FieldValue.serverTimestamp(),
1008       isSharded: aggregatedFeatureScans.length > 1,
1009       missingAddresses: afterData.preprocessing.ignoredWallets,
1010       failedWallets: failedWallets
1011     }
1012   },
1013   featuresCompleted: {
1014     [featureId]: 'success'
1015   }
1016 }, { merge: true });
1017
1018 // Commit the batch
1019 await batch.commit();
1020
1021 await admin.database().ref(`/scans/${scanId}/features/${featureId}/analysis/status`).set(analysingStatus);
1022
1023 return null;
1024
1025 }
1026
1027 }
```

6.4.5. Final Scan UI

After the Scan has finally completed, it will show each feature's abstracted (but important) information on the scan page (Figure 67) (Figure 68). If the user wishes to enhance and see more granular information, they can click on each individual feature (Figure 69) (Figure 70).

Figure 67 - Scan Brief [Desktop]

Figure 68 - Scan Brief [Mobile]

Figure 69 - SharedHeldTokens Detailed [Desktop]

My Scans > Scan > Shared Held Tokens

Shared Held Tokens

Below is a list of tokens that are held by multiple wallets.

Search by name...

Status Columns Download CSV

Total 603 tokens Rows per page: 10

	NAME	WALLETS
☐	DxnODE 0xd23d86EF506f20E959d8Ad9b83e9C450157Bb904	3
☐	Azazel Coin 0xf302577E752678a9D878FC18317f4C791A57A6Da	3
☐	Azrael 0x88a264F970692B07d0142409a58144C478DE3b0b	3
☐	Back Into Battle 0x18671a89488C656f16c579147F6070098ec5768	3
☐	Bull Step 0xd82CA720E13E69B025cA0A14535D00cc4256f74	3
☐	Conor Token 0xF16260CF0928e8f84606247e2a35Fb87cb0dfD9	3
☐	Dojo Finance 0xf10D0679314AdCe5Bcb1cf7C85FD75344D583a33	3
☐	Elenidas 0x527ba3d6AB9f1244a97019656f9D4f2cD94CA2d3	3
☐	Grok1.5 0xc7089108c0f351E86A9934189f42682541496392	3
☐	Homer Simpson 0xFDBFA759118C6F880C385842cD98c19a03b32722	3

1 2 3 4 5 ... 61 >

0 of 10 selected

Monthly Scans
17 / 150 used
WHALE

Account Settings Log Out

Figure 70 - SharedHeldTokens Detailed [Mobile]

6.5. CI/CD & Deployment via Vercel & GitHub

Below demonstrates the CI/CD used in development.

Figure 71 - Vercel CI/CD Flow

6.6. Testing

It's worth noting that these tests are limited due to the sheer size of the project. Only necessary tests are done relating to Scanning and Adding Wallets. Tests were done throughout the project unofficially and vigorously.

Table 1 - WalletScan Testing Table

Test + Expected + Actual	Screenshot(s)	
<p>Test: Add wallet</p> <p>Expected: Adds</p> <p>Actual: Adds</p>	<p>The first screenshot shows the 'Add Wallet' dialog with the following fields: 'Wallet Address' (0x8314f27666944FEB78e16d5311a94D23), 'Wallet Name' (jetlijonny.eth), and 'Tags' (+). There are color selection circles and an 'Add Wallet' button. The second screenshot shows the wallet list with three items: 'jetlijonny.eth' (0x8314f27666944FEB78e16d5311a94D23DA6E4ID5), 'walletUnnamed' (0xB7b6d2f4AA2a1e87702576c29EBd5ceD0D7CE04e), and 'howcanibehomophobic' (0x7431931094e8BAe1ECAA7D0b57d2284e121F760e).</p>	
<p>Test: Delete Wallet</p> <p>Expected: Deleted</p> <p>Actual: Deleted</p>	<p>The first screenshot shows the wallet list with three items: 'jetlijonny.eth', 'walletUnnamed', and 'howcanibehomophobic'. The second screenshot shows the same list, but 'jetlijonny.eth' is missing, and a success message 'Wallet deleted successfully' is displayed at the bottom.</p>	

Test: Update Wallet Name

Expected: "walletChanged"

Actual: "walletChanged"

Test: Create Scan – 4
Wallets – 2 Features

Expected: 2 Features, 1
Detailed, No errors

Actual: Success

Test: View All Scans

Expected: View All Scans

Actual: Success

7. Testing & Evaluation Strategy

In the Testing & Evaluation section, the dissertation assesses the project's success in meeting its requirements. This includes evaluating the impact of the project and how well it achieves its objectives. The section analyzes survey results from the developer and the main evidence of implementation to determine the project's alignment with its specified requirements and objectives.

The survey (- **Survey Result - Appendix 1**) targeted the developer responsible for WalletScan, gathering insights on their experience with serverless architectures and blockchain technology, the challenges faced, and the overall development process. The developer, with six years of web development experience, had prior exposure to blockchain but described their familiarity with serverless architectures as only "somewhat" knowledgeable before starting the project.

Key findings from the survey reveal that while the developer found serverless technologies (specifically Google Cloud Functions) fairly robust, scoring a 7 out of 10, there were notable challenges. These included issues with integrating third-party APIs like Transpose.io and handling data irregularities from blockchain sources. Despite these issues, the developer confirmed that the technology stack was effectively chosen, meeting the project's needs, and allowing for easy deployment via Vercel. This was further supported by an overall satisfaction rating of 8 out of 10.

The serverless model was found to be cost-effective, although managing costs associated with serverless services like Google Cloud's Secret Manager proved to be more complex than anticipated.

In terms of security and deployment, the use of environment variables and strict permissions for GitHub merging played crucial roles. The CI/CD pipeline facilitated smooth deployments across development, staging, and production environments, although initial deployments were plagued with failures mostly due to untested code pushes.

The developer recommended improvements for debugging tools within Google's serverless environment and highlighted the ease of deploying updates as a major advantage. They also

noted the steep learning curve associated with proprietary serverless platforms and expressed a preference for more control over the development process.

From these insights, it is evident that while serverless architectures offer significant benefits such as scalability, cost efficiency, and ease of deployment, they also introduce specific challenges that can affect the performance and development experience.

Despite these operational challenges, the developer appreciated the rapid deployment capabilities of serverless platforms and their built-in security features, which significantly simplified project management and reduced time-to-market—key advantages for a Web3 application like WalletScan where scalability and performance are critical.

Overall, the developer's satisfaction with the development process was positive, with an 8 out of 10 rating. This reflects a successful adaptation to serverless technology despite the hurdles encountered. The feedback gathered provides invaluable insights into refining future project workflows and technology choices for similar Web3 applications. This aligns with the dissertation's aim to explore the practicalities and real-world implications of using serverless architectures to build scalable Web3 applications, providing a nuanced perspective that supports the broader academic discussion of these technologies.

8. Conclusion

This dissertation has nicely demonstrated the synergy between serverless computing and blockchain technology through the development of WalletScan, a scalable Web3 wallet aggregation application. The findings confirm that serverless architectures can enhance the efficiency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness of blockchain-based applications, aligning with the evolving needs of digital economies. Despite encountering specific technical challenges such as integration complexities with third-party APIs and managing data irregularities from blockchain sources, the serverless model upheld its promise of operational agility and rapid deployment capabilities!

The research has highlighted the pivotal role of serverless environments in reducing the overhead associated with traditional server management, thereby allowing developers to focus more on application functionality rather than infrastructure. However, the results also pointed out the necessity for improved debugging tools and the challenges posed by the proprietary nature of serverless platforms which sometimes restrict developer control over the process.

8.1. Recommendations

Enhanced Debugging Tools: Future serverless platforms should consider offering more robust debugging and monitoring tools to better support developers in troubleshooting and optimising their applications.

Education and Documentation: As serverless technology continues to evolve, there is a need for updated and comprehensive documentation that can help developers understand and navigate the complex landscape of serverless architecture more effectively.

Cost Management Strategies: Developers should be equipped with better tools and methodologies for predicting and managing costs associated with serverless technologies to prevent unexpected expenses and optimise resource utilisation.

8.2. Further Research

Long-Term Performance Analysis: Further studies could focus on the long-term performance and scalability of serverless architectures in real-world blockchain applications, providing deeper insights into sustainability and costs.

This dissertation has laid a foundational understanding of the interplay between serverless computing and blockchain technology, setting the stage for future innovations and research that could potentially reshape the landscape of digital finance and Web3 applications. The practical experience and insights gained from developing WalletScan serve as a valuable resource for both academic scholars and industry practitioners aiming to leverage these technologies to create impactful and scalable solutions.

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10. Appendices

Figure 72 - Survey Result - Appendix 1

How many years of experience do you have in software development?
6

How familiar were you with serverless architectures before working on WalletScan?
Somewhat

Have you worked on blockchain technology prior to this project?
Yes

What programming languages and frameworks are you most comfortable with?
Python, HTMX, Javascript, Typescript, Java, Kotlin, React, Django

Rate your experience with the serverless technologies used in WalletScan (Google Cloud Functions).
7 / 10

How effective were the tools and technologies chosen for developing WalletScan in terms of ease of integration and usability?
6 / 10

What challenges did you face while integrating blockchain technology with serverless architectures?
- Integrating Transpose.io's API - Problems with null values from the blockchain and scam characters (long values for strings) - Finding resources and forums for guidance - Figuring out security and best practices when adding wallets. - Figuring out how to setup Staging, Development and Production environment for testing Alchemy API. Alchemy API was not implemented due to time constraints.

Did the chosen technology stack meet the needs of the project? Why or why not?
Absolutely.

Describe the ease or difficulty of deploying updates and changes to WalletScan.
Deploying to Vercel was extremely easy and straight-forward by simply pushing to GitHub and merging. It's great to see the staging version of the website! There was difficulty in easily setting up environment variables with Vercel as there was so many.

How effective was the CI/CD pipeline in managing deployments across different environments (dev, staging, production)?
7 / 10

How often did deployments fail, and what were the common reasons?
Deployments failed quite a lot during the start of development of the project due to me not checking and building the project locally beforehand. Many errors to do with using apostrophes instead of escape characters. There was a large amount of typescript-based errors which caused issues too.

What steps were taken to ensure the security and integrity of deployments?
Environment variables being used was absolutely crucial. Also the github has to ensure the right person can merge based on permissions.

How did serverless architecture impact the performance and scalability of WalletScan?

3 / 10

What tools or methods were used to monitor and optimize the application performance?

The main tools used were the Google Cloud Console for debugging purposes as well as the Vercel dashboard when looking at deployments as well as Vercel's logs.

Was the serverless model cost-effective compared to traditional server-based models?

Yes

Did you encounter any issues related to cost management with serverless services?

Yes

How did you manage the budget for cloud resources and third-party services?

The budget management wasn't considered that much. Only optimisations were put in place such as caching in the right places to avoid high costs.

Were there any unexpected costs, and how were they handled?

Yes. I noticed that using Google Cloud Secret Manager with a ton of environment variables (for the Cloud Functions) took up a bulk of the money paid (around ~\$2). That was with one user.

How would you rate your overall satisfaction with the development process of WalletScan?

8 / 10

What improvements would you suggest for the development workflow and tooling?

With Google, the Functions Console is horrendously complicated for debugging. For Vercel, the tracebacks for deployment errors are not that detailed.

What was the most time-consuming part of the development process?

At the beginning, the most time-consuming part was the pre-implementation, figuring out how to design such an architecture to create Wallet Scans in a scalable way. During development, it was debugging and testing the scanning functionality. This took a very long time due to having to wait for multiple function deployments to the cloud as local development testing was slightly infeasible.

Were there sufficient resources and support available for problem-solving during development?

Yes

Based on your experience, what are the key benefits and drawbacks of using serverless architectures for Web3 applications?

Serverless architectures offer a scalable, cost-effective approach that really shines in Web3 applications, allowing me to focus more on the application logic instead of getting bogged down by infrastructure management. The integration with blockchain technologies is particularly smooth, which is a huge advantage given the often unpredictable workloads we see with Web3 projects. Deploying a website using serverless solutions like Firebase is also incredibly quick and straightforward compared to traditional server setups, such as those on DigitalOcean. With serverless, security features and authentication are often built-in; Firebase Auth, for example, manages security robustly right out of the

box, so I don't have to. Furthermore, Firestore, as a NoSQL database within Firebase, is perfect for handling the varied and sometimes unpredictable data structures common in blockchain applications, because it doesn't require a fixed schema. However, there are some drawbacks to consider, like cold starts, more complex state management, and limited customisation options. The email system was easy to setup, but lacked a lot of customisation. Additionally, the risk of vendor lock-in is something to watch out for when going serverless as I noticed that when building WalletScan, a lot of it is using custom firebase and vercel packages throughout for interaction, and if I wanted to leave Firebase or Vercel and use my own things, I'd have to completely rewrite API routes, a lot of code.

- Would you recommend serverless architectures for similar projects? Why or why not?

Yes. I would because of the relatively faster time to market. It is so quick to get deployed and online and ready to go. You don't have to deal with security too much either. pretty much free too.
- What lessons did you learn from working on this project that you would apply to future projects?

I learnt that it was slightly tedious to learn proprietary serverless platform integration code and that I have way less control, but faster deployment time and less worry.
- How do you see the future of serverless and blockchain technologies evolving in the industry?

To be quite honest, I have a feeling blockchain web applications will start to become more prominent with the use and evolvement of serverless technologies, making it super easy to get crypto websites out there.

Figure 73 - Appendix 2 - Gantt Chart Progress